

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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PUBLIC HEALTH NURSES ENHANCING OUTCOMES OF CARE
COORDINATION AMONG CHILDREN AND YOUTH IN FOSTER CARE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this DNP project is to develop, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based nursing practice guideline at two Los Angeles County Department of Children and Family Services (LACDCFS) offices to enhance care coordination activities of public health nurses (PHN) to improve medical and dental compliance rates among children and youth in foster care (FC). The LACDCFS medical and dental compliance goal is 90%. The two offices in this project have significantly lower examination completion rates below 50%.

This performance improvement project included conducting focus groups of PHNs and SWs regarding their perceptions of challenges, barriers, and quality improvement of care coordination. The results from the focus group were integrated along with best practice strategies were used to revise the PHN roles and responsibility protocol. PHNs were educated on the revised practice guideline to work in partnership with other disciplines and foster care parents, thus facilitating the completion of children's health exams. Data analysis included the comparison of data before and after implementation of the practice guideline. The data included numbers of collaboration, communication activities, completed medical and dental exams and the office compliance rates.

Following guideline implementation, the number of consultations, communication activities completed, and health assessments entered into the LACDCFS collection

system improved and medical exam compliance rate increased five percent; however, dental compliance decreased by two percent. Concurrent system issues including information technology glitches, vacant PHN positions, lack of readily access to child records, and mixed responsibilities between PHNs and SWs limited full implementation of the PHN role and responsibilities protocol.

It is recommended that nursing administration immediately hire and train PHNs to fully staff the offices. A six-month timeline should be created with the initial goal of attaining a medical exam compliance rate of 75% and dental 50%. It is recommended PHNs have more authority and unfettered access to medical records so they may perform their job duties more efficiently. PHNs should attend Supervising SW unit meetings to provide the unit with monthly compliance rates reports. Supportive staff should receive additional training to appropriately assist SWs and PHNs with care coordination. Regular meetings with child welfare staff, PHNs, community providers and caregivers will enhance ongoing communication. This project has implications for clinical practice in care coordination. Effective communication and collaboration among all staff members, CG, and HCP is important to enhance care coordination for the optimal health outcomes of children and youth in foster care.

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BACKGROUND

Children and adolescents are placed into the foster care (FC) system because of maltreatment, abuse, or neglect by their parent(s) or caregiver(s). In 2015, there were 28,000 children and youth placed in FC throughout Los Angeles County (Child Welfare Information Gateway, 2017). Children in FC receive state Medicaid benefits through Title IV-E of the Social Security Act qualifying them to receive medical and dental care services (Palmer, Marton, Yelowitz, & Talbert, 2017). Los Angeles County Department of Children and Family Services (LACDCFS) is responsible for ensuring children and youth in FC receive medical and dental care. The LACDCFS policy requires that all children and youth entering FC have an initial medical assessment within 24 hours of placement and a comprehensive physical exam within 30 days and every year thereafter, unless the child is younger than 24 months of age or their medical condition requires more frequent monitoring and care (Szilagyi, Rosen, Rubin, & Zlotnik, 2015). The LACDCFS also requires children and youth in FC have a dental exam completed beginning at one-year of age and every six months after that (LACDCFS, 2018). To receive medical and dental care on time, children must have their care coordinated by healthcare providers (HCP), caregivers (CG), social workers (SW), and public health nurses (PHN). Many children do not receive preventive care when entering or during their time in FC, nor the necessary care coordination when changing FC placements or exiting the FC system (Deans et al., 2015).

Significance

Physical Health Outcomes

Children in FC have more medical diagnoses (4.2% vs. 3.1%) compared to children who have no child welfare involvement (Turney & Wildeman, 2016). Up to 80% of children entering FC have unmet needs for medical conditions, with asthma and diabetes mellitus being the most prevalent (Schneiderman, Smith, & Palinkas, 2012; Szilagyi et al., 2015). According to Turney and Wildeman (2016) children in FC are more likely to have asthma (18%), obesity (24%), and visual and hearing deficits (7.3%) when compared to children with the same condition, asthma (8.7%), obesity (15/7%), and visual and hearing deficits (2.5%) not in FC. Eighty-eight percent of children in FC require a referral to a healthcare specialist for more detailed assessment, monitoring, and/or treatment of medical conditions (Deutsch & Fortin, 2015).

Dental Health Outcomes

In addition to having neglected medical conditions, 40% of children in FC also have significant dental problems (Szilagyi et al., 2015). Unmet dental needs can cause tooth decay which can lead to medical conditions such as sinus and ear infections (Holtby, Zahnd, & Grant, 2015). Poor dental health can impair a child's ability to focus, thus leading to poor school performance (Holtby et al., 2015). According to Melbye, Huebner, Chi, Hinderberger, and Milgrom (2013), children in FC receive irregular dental care and tend to have more dental caries and poorer oral health than children residing at home with biological parent (s).

Medical and Dental Compliance

Children placed in the FC system do not receive comprehensive timely healthcare (Schneiderman, 2006). The LACDCFS goal for both medical and dental examination compliance is 90%. The data in Table 1 shows the medical and dental compliance rates at several child welfare offices in Los Angeles County.

Table 1

LACDCFS Medical and Dental Compliance Rates

LACDCFS Office	Medical Compliance Rate	Dental Compliance Rate
American Indian Unit	90%	77%
Santa Fe Springs	83%	68%
Glendora	77%	58%
Pomona	71%	57%
Compton	57%	28%
Torrance	44%	18%

Note. LACDCFS = Los Angeles County Department of Children and Family Services

Except for the medical examination compliance in the office for the American Indian Unit, the compliance rates in some of the higher performing units/offices with medical compliance of 70% and higher do not meet the agency's established goal of 90%. Dental compliance is below target in all offices. The Compton and Torrance offices have significantly lower rates when compared to the compliance rates of the higher performing offices. Because children in FC are at higher risk of having medical conditions than their peers who are not in FC, compliance with medical and dental exams are critical to the overall health and well-being of this population of children and youth.

Public Health Nurse and Social Workers

The LACDCFS employs SWs and PHNs to ensure the safety and well-being of children in FC. The SWs main priority is investigating allegations of abuse and neglect, and their focus is on child protection and safety. The role of the PHN is to “provide comprehensive health care consultations to SWs to prevent illness and promote and maintain the health of children and youth in foster care” (LACDCFS, 2018, p. 2). Tasks of PHNs in FC include identifying chronic physical, developmental, and mental conditions in children, and reviewing and assessing all medical documentation and reports. PHNs also provide education on child-specific conditions and sexual health education to adolescents, SWs, and CGs, and status reports to LACDCFS administrative staff on critical incident, media alert, near fatality, and child fatality cases (LACDCFS, 2018). PHNs and SWs are not formally educated on each other’s roles or duties in child welfare. Therefore, PHNs may not comprehend why scheduling children’s health appointments may not be a top priority for the SW. Child welfare professionals may lack the understanding about each other’s professional role and different responsibilities and concerns which may cause a child’s care to be “fragmented and crisis-oriented rather than planned and preventive” (Szilagi et al., 2015)

Because SWs are not trained in nursing or medicine, they may not always recognize when a child in FC needs medical attention. Therefore, SWs rely on PHNs for assistance in coordinating and monitoring medical and dental exams for children in FC. Children’s cases are managed by SWs whose duty per agency policy, is to consult and collaborate with PHNs to coordinate a child’s health care. Knowing the roles and responsibilities of everyone working with children in FC is essential for effective

collaboration (Selleck et al., 2017). When professionals from different backgrounds come together to coordinate a patient's care, better health outcomes are achieved (Engel, Prentice, & Taplay, 2017).

Care Coordination

The term care coordination (CC) refers to the practice of assisting with facilitating the delivery of comprehensive health promotion, and chronic disease management (Looman et al., 2013). In addition, CC refers to the use of communications skills to develop connections among medical providers, families, and health professionals (Looman et al., 2013). The child welfare system continues to have challenges in ensuring that preventive health exams and the well-being of children in FC is achieved due to the inefficiencies of the system and the lack of care coordination between health care provider and the children welfare system (Schneiderman, 2006). In LACDCFS, PHNs provide CC with CGs, HCPs, school nurses, probation officers, and other community agencies to maintain a child's continuity of care. CGs have a responsibility to schedule and take children to medical and dental exams appointments and play an essential role in ensuring children in FC receive adequate health care (Schneiderman et al., 2012).

Professional collaboration and CC can lead to improved comprehensive care for patients with complicated health conditions (Selleck et al., 2017). PHNs who take the lead on CC activities can potentially increase the number of children who receive medical and dental exams. An increased awareness of the roles of PHNs, SWs, CGs, and medical providers and an evidence-based procedural guideline may assist with improving the CC of children's health screening and increase the medical and dental examination compliance rates of LACDCFS Compton and Torrance offices

Problem Statement

Under the current LACDCFS policy, it is the responsibility of the SWs, as case managers for children in FC, to initiate contact with PHNs regarding a child's care. However, SWs have high caseloads and different case priorities, which often prevents them from contacting and consulting with the PHN within a reasonable time-frame. While PHNs can initiate contact with SWs, they often do not because of their own high caseload count, patient acuity levels, and the lack of the foster care department's PHN practice guideline mandating them to do so. The lack of time and different styles of communication are barriers to effective SW and PHN collaboration (Gould, Lee, Berkowitz, & Bronstein, 2015).

Baccalaureate prepared PHNs have state certification which allows them to perform CC activities independently and before formal consultations with SWs is requested. By initiating contact with SWs, PHNs could minimize delays in needed care, resulting in children receiving mandated and essential medical and dental exams on-time. By initiating contact with SWs, the PHNs demonstrates working within the full scope of practice for the role, which in turn benefits the health of children in FC (Kiwanuka, Boyar, & Jensen, 2013). If PHNs do not make the first contact with the SWs when necessary, CC is delayed or not being performed effectively causing fragmented and less than optimal care for children and youth in foster care.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project was to develop, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based nursing practice guideline at LACDCFS, Compton and Torrance offices, to enhance the care coordination activity of PHNs to increase their updating of completed

medical and dental health exams, thereby increasing the medical and dental compliance rates among children and youth in FC. This project will include education on the CC roles of both PHNs and SWs.

Objectives:

1. Develop a practice guideline on CC with input from Los Angeles County, Department of Public Health, Children's Medical Services Educational Team and Child Welfare Public Health Nursing, Foster Care Program Nurse Manager. in the field.
2. Provide policy training to PHNs in Torrance and Compton offices.

The expected outcomes of this project are to increase PHN care coordination efforts as measured by consults and communication activities to increase the medical and dental compliance rates for children in FC after three to four months of intervention implementation.

Conceptual Framework

The Public Health Nursing Practice Model

The PHN practice model is an instructive guide for the application of community and population-based public health nursing practice (Figure 1). This model focuses on populations with similar health issues and characteristics. The PHN practice model's foundation comes from the Quad Council of Public Health Nursing Organizations and the Minnesota Department of Health, PHN section (Los Angeles County, Department of Public Health, 2015) In practice, the PHN completes an assessment of data relevant to the health status of a specific population, analyzes the data to form a diagnosis that is a priority to the people, identifies desired

outcomes, and creates a plan to accomplish the expected results (LACDPH, 2015). Once the plan is established, the PHN will implement the plan by collaborating with others and providing CC, health education, consultations, and other regulatory activities. The nursing process finishes with an evaluation of the health status of the population (LACDPH, 2015). The PHN practice model is an instructive guide for the application of community and population-based public health nursing practice.

Figure 1. Public Health Nursing Practice Model (Smith & Bazini-Barakat, 2003).

The PRECEDE-PROCEED Model

Dr. Larry Green and Dr. Marshall Kreuter created the PRECEDE-PROCEED model (PPM) (Appendix B) to provide a systematic method of reducing morbidity and mortality in communities through the assessment of a population's health and quality of life needs for developing, planning, implementing, and evaluating health promotion interventions or programs (Crosby & Noar, 2011; Green & Mercer, 2002). PRECEDE is

an acronym that stands for predisposing, reinforcing, and enabling constructs in education and environment, and diagnosis and evaluation (Tramm, 2012 p.138). The PRECEDE part of the model has five assessment phases: social, epidemiological, behavioral and environmental, educational and organizational, and administrative and policy (Crosby & Noar, 2011). The results of the assessment phases helps to identify the population's needs and health goals and determine and directs the actions that should be completed before implementing any intervention. PRECEDE begins with the identification of a quality of life outcome and then works backwards from the desired goal (Crosby & Noar, 2011). PROCEED stands for policy, regulatory and organization constructs in education and environment development; it is a roadmap for intervention implementation (Crosby, 2011). The four phases in PROCEED help move the project toward the desired goal and characterize the actions taken in implementing a health promotion education and/or policy intervention. Then, an evaluation is done on the intervention's process and its impact on the population's diagnosed problem or issue. Later, an outcome evaluation is completed to determine if the intervention has improved or enhanced the health and quality of life of the population (Green & Mercer, 2002).

Phase one of PPM calls for the assessment of social factors to assist with the identification of a health issue or concern that is impacting the quality of life of a community or population. Data on the population's demographics, current health status, needs and risk factors can be obtained from interviews, questionnaires, clinics, and professional literature (Green & Mercer, 2002).

Figure 2. The PRECEDE-PROCEED Model adapted from (Green & Kreuter, 1999, p. 35).

Phase two is the epidemiological assessment of the current health status of the community or population where vital statistics, such as morbidity and mortality data, state and national health surveys, medical and administrative records are assessed (Crosby & Noar, 2011). The result of phase one and two assessments leads to the identification of the population's health priorities and problems. Then, measurable intervention objectives and achievable goals can be developed.

Phase three involves assessing the behavioral and environmental determinants of the health problem or issue (Tramm, McCarthy, & Yates, 2012). Assessment of the population's knowledge, perceptions and cultural practices, and social circumstances is completed to identify modifiable factors that can be changed and used to set intervention priorities and direct planning activities (Crosby & Noar, 2011).

In phase four, an educational and organizational assessment of three elements of factors that predispose, reinforce, and enable behaviors is completed (Crosby & Noar, 2011). First, the predisposing factors serve to analyze the population's attitudes, viewpoints, values, or thoughts that can either facilitate or hinder change (Crosby & Noar, 2011). Enabling factors are those that would help the population accept and maintain healthy or unhealthy behaviors and lifestyles or embrace or reject environmental conditions such as available resources and access to care and services. (Crosby & Noar, 2011; Tramm et al., 2012). Lastly, reinforcing factors are behaviors and attitudes that have influential power and can ensure the desired behaviors recurs (Tramm et al., 2012).

Administrative and policy assessment is completed in phase five which has two components. First, it involves deciding on the health promotion, education, or policy intervention that will be used to change the behavior or environmental factor identified in phase four and the factors that will support it. Secondly, administrative concerns or requirements that must be addressed prior to implementing the intervention, procedure change, or program are reviewed (Crosby & Noar, 2011). This assessment considers the financial resources available to carry out an intervention or program, and assess whether additional staff or other department agencies will need to be involved. Decisions in this phase can facilitate or hinder the implementation of an intervention (Crosby & Noar, 2011). For organizational acceptance, the proposed intervention must align with the organization's mission, vision, values, and policies (Tramm et al., 2012).

Phase six is the implementation phase and begins the PROCEED portion of the model. In this phase, the intervention or program based on the assessment and planning completed in the PRECEDE phases of the PPM is implemented (Crosby & Noar, 2011).

Phases seven through nine evaluate the process, impact, and outcome of the intervention or program implemented on the population's health and quality of life.

Process evaluation is about the procedure; it determines whether the plan is implemented accordingly and if intervention objectives are met. If objectives are not met, adjustments can be made (Crosby & Noar, 2011). Impact evaluation determines whether the intervention has the intended effect on the predisposing, enabling and reinforcing factors regarding behaviors and/or the environment as previously identified (Crosby & Noar, 2011). Finally, outcome evaluation examines whether the intervention or program goals were met in changing the health and social benefits or quality of life of the population or community (Green & Mercer, 2002).

Application of Models

This project used both the PHN Practice model and the PPM to guide the development, implementation, and evaluation of a PHN CC guideline. Both models are grounded in public health (nursing and education) and recognize the need to assess/diagnose aspects of the identified problem that affects health and quality of life of the persons, populations, or communities served. The value of combining the models lies in the elaboration of each step in the project's planned development, implementation, and evaluation. The combined model (Figure 3) showed the models' integration and application to the problem of inadequate medical and dental care for children in FC due to the non-existent or poor CC.

For this project, the PHN practice model guided PHNs to assess the health needs and priorities for children in FC, and the PPM directed the nurse through an in-depth

assessment, starting with the identification of the population's health outcome goal of timely medical and dental examinations.

Health status was assessed by reviewing the LACDCFS internal data system, which revealed a decrease of medical and dental exam compliance rates in the Compton and Torrance offices and the increased rates of unmanaged chronic health conditions, visual and hearing deficits and poor oral care (Turney & Wildeman, 2016; Szilagyi et al., 2015). Parental behavior of not giving attention to a child's health needs, not providing healthy behavior education such as daily teeth brushing, and unstable home environments and/or homes where physical and sexual abuse or neglect occur, are directly related to children not receiving health examinations and care (Lalayants, 2013; Szilagi et al., 2015). Completion of behavior and environmental assessments allowed the nurse to make diagnoses as outlined in the PHN practice model. The diagnosed problem is that a lack of CC leads to decreased medical and dental exam compliance rates that can have a negative impact on the quality of life for children in FC. This project focused on improving poor CC or the lack of CC.

The PPM continued with an educational and organizational assessment of the factors that can support or impede outcomes. For this project, the lack of CC, knowledge of the PHN and SW role and priorities, and children moving frequently to multiple FC home placements were predisposing factors considered when trying to improve CC. The PHN practice model referred to this part of the project as the planning phase. The reinforcing factors included support for PHNs, SWs, and foster parents/caregiver that will enhance CC. The factors leading to improved CC are enhanced communication, all FC children having Medi-Cal insurance, and children having access to FC specific medical

clinics will increase the sustainability of a policy guideline aimed at influencing the number of completed health exams.

Administrative and policy factors indicated there were no additional funding or staffing required to implement a CC nurse practice guideline. In addition to training on the CC guideline, education will be provided to the PHN regarding SW functions for role clarification. The organization's current policy on PHNs' caseloads will be reviewed to assess equitable workloads according to the memorandum of understanding for discussion with the nursing administrative team. The proposed intervention did not have any organizational conflicts, it aligned with the LACDPH mission of improving the well-being of populations by promoting health and preventing disease among county residents.

During the implementation phase of the PPM model, a revised PHN roles and responsibilities nursing practice guideline was implemented to increase and enhance the CC activities of PHNs. The aim was to improve CC and the number of health exams completed on children placed in foster care in the LACDCFS Torrance and Compton offices. As the project was implemented, ongoing evaluation was done to ensure the practice guideline was implemented according to plan.

Both models conclude with an evaluation phase. After a month of implementation, the PHN practice CC guideline was evaluated for any issues or problems that require adjustment. The effectiveness of the practice guideline was reviewed to evaluate its impact on PHNs CC activities, the number of health exams completed on children in FC, and the LACDCFS Torrance and Compton office compliance rates.

Figure 3. Public Health Nursing Practice Model and PRECEDE-PROCEED Model adapted from (Smith & Bazini-Barakat, 2003; Green & Kreuter, 1999).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

This DNP project included the revision, implementation, and evaluation of a PHN practice guideline to enhance CC activities of PHNs in the LACDCFS Torrance and Compton child welfare offices. A focused approach was used to search the literature for articles related to CC in the child welfare system, other pediatric settings, and collaboration between PHNs, SWs, caregivers, and health providers. Because it is important to understand factors contributing to CC, a search of the literature was done to evaluate the impact and influence of collaboration and communication on CC. A search was conducted using PubMed, MEDLINE, Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature, Google Scholar, PsycINFO, Social Science (EBSCO), and the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHQR) website. The search was limited to peer-reviewed journal articles published in the English language. To capture healthcare information published after the implementation of the Affordable Care Act in 2010 which may have impacted children in FC, the date range of January 2009 to March 2018 was used. The key terms used for this search included care coordination, case management, child welfare system, child protective services, and interprofessional collaboration. Additional search terms and combination of terms for each topic and number of articles found are listed in Table 2.

Table 2.

Literature Search Specific Search Terms and Search Term Combinations

Topic	Search Term Combinations	Total Articles
Care Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care coordination OR case management • Child welfare system AND care coordination • Protective services AND care coordination • Care coordination AND other pediatric settings • Health outcomes AND care coordination 	223
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration AND interprofessional • Child welfare AND collaboration AND nurse • Collaboration AND social worker • Collaboration AND nurse AND social worker 	345
Google Scholar Search: 2009-2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care coordination, case management and child welfare system or protective services 	1520
Agency for Health Care Quality & Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care coordination 	N/A
National Quality Forum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care Coordination 	N/A

Articles were reviewed for relevance to the project and systematically arranged into two main categories: care coordination and collaboration.

Table 3

Total Number of Articles Used for Project

Category	Total Number of Articles Used
Care Coordination	26
Collaboration in Child Welfare	20

Care Coordination

The rising cost of healthcare continues to place an economic burden on the U.S. healthcare system. Changes in the healthcare industry require cost-efficient coordinated care. CC refers to the intentional practice activities of organizing, assisting and facilitating the delivery of comprehensive health promotion and chronic disease management for a patient or client (AHRQ, 2018; Cady, Kelly, Finkelstein, Looman, & Garwick, 2014; Looman et al., 2013; NFQ, 2010; Robinson, 2010; Segal & DuGoff, 2014). Other terms used to describe CC are case management and managed care. In CC, the patient should be included and at the center of all care decisions. Pertinent to this project, children in FC have unmet health needs and can benefit from effective CC to ensure they receive routine medical and dental care and management and monitoring of chronic health conditions (Schneiderman et al., 2012; Selleck et al., 2017; Szilagyi et al., 2015).

Care Coordination and Health Outcomes

Research studies showed that children have improved health outcomes when their care is coordinated (Berry et al., 2011; Litt & McCormick, 2015; Schneiderman et al., 2012). A study of children at pediatric asthma clinics in Los Angeles, Chicago, Philadelphia and San Juan, Puerto Rico determined that children had greater asthma symptom control when a staff member performed CC activities; children had 2.22 fewer day symptoms ($p = <.01$), 1.9 fewer night symptoms ($p = <.01$), fewer emergency room visits, and fewer hospitalizations (Janevic et al., 2016). A study of seven U.S. spina bifida clinics found CC activities resulted in increased access to and continuity of care and

decreased burden on families when the child's appointments were scheduled for the same day (Brustrom, Thibadeau, John, Liesmann, & Rose, 2012).

A study completed in a pediatric cardiology ambulatory setting measured patient outcomes based on the result of CC interaction/activity and found that there were fewer clinic visits (17.1%), fewer emergency room visits (8.6%), and 71 (12.4%) fewer possible medication errors (Connor et al., 2018). Additionally, Connor et al. (2018) reported a \$550,458 savings from adverse outcomes prevented in addition, to savings related to unplanned resource utilization including the prevention of urgent care (\$158,564) and emergency room visits (\$153,566). The literature supports the use of CC activities to improve patient health outcomes and recognizes CC is a vital aspect of providing quality care that can change the approach, enhance the quality and provide better access to HC across the lifespan. (Brustrom et al., 2012; Cady et al., 2014; Connor, 2018; Janevic et al., 2016; Schultz, Pineda, Lonhart, Davies, & McDonald, 2013). Additionally, inadequate or lack of CC can compromise a patient's care and increase their risk of negative health outcomes (Cady et al., 2014; Schultz et al., 2013).

The Provision of Care Coordination

The method of delivery of CC varied across studies and was dependent upon the setting. Some medical clinics had a designated care coordinator, schools utilized school nurses, child welfare departments used a mix of social workers, nurses, and caregivers to coordinate the care of children in FC (Brustrom, Thibadeau, John, Liesmann, & Rose, 2012; Schneiderman, 2008; Schneiderman et al., 2012). While the delivery of CC changed with the environment, CC procedures did not. The literature was congruent in identifying tasks such as connecting patients to primary care, specialty providers, and

community and financial resources, supporting families in self-management of diseases, medication monitoring, and developing a plan of care which includes follow-up as CC activities (AHRQ, 2018; Berry et al., 2011; Brustrom et al., 2012; NFQ, 2010; Schultz, Pineda, Lonhart, Davies, & McDonald, 2013).

Measuring Care Coordination

National organizations and healthcare systems increasingly realize the importance of identifying valid and trustworthy measurements of coordinated activities. A systematic evaluation of 259 studies concluded that most evaluations of CC are based on the satisfaction of care expressed by family members, patients, and others who represent a system or patient through the completion of surveys or questionnaires (Schultz et al., 2013). In addition, some studies included recorded CC activity data from the review of medical records and administrative claims to measure CC (Schultz et al., 2013). The review of literature identifies and supports these CC activity domains as essential components of performance and to gage if CC is comprehensively measured (NFQ, 2010; Schultz et al., 2013). Researchers used tools to measure CC activities by domains such as those listed in Table 3 (NFQ, 2010; Schultz et al., 2013; Segal & DuGoff, 2014).

Measurement domains of CC activity can be assessed and useful in supporting and ensuring children in FC receive health exams. Establishing accountability is when an individual is identified as the person responsible for coordinating a child's care, when that responsibility is transferred to another care member of the child welfare team, and when it is known who is accountable and will respond to the failure of any aspect of care. Communication is a measurement domain that is focused on sharing and transferring information. PHNs, SWs, and CGs should provide a child's health history to the HCP

that would allow for them to complete a thorough needs assessment and a proactive plan of care. Standardized measures can be established from the identification of CC domains to find and address the gaps in CC and measure its effectiveness in eliminating fragmented care. Therefore, it is important that coordination procedures are examined and evaluated to guide and support the development of CC PHN guidelines and policies.

Table 4

Care Coordination Activity (Domains)

Measurement Domains
Establish Accountability
Communication
Facilitate Transitions
Needs Assessment and Goals
Develop a Plan of Care
Monitor & Follow Up
Link to Community Resources
Referrals to specialty providers

Barriers and Facilitators to Care Coordination

Lack of time, inadequate or differing communication skills, organizational policies, and unclear professional roles were identified as the most frequent barriers to CC (Camicia et al., 2013; Deans et al., 2015; Tschudy et al., 2016). The lack of functioning health information systems and availability of community resources in specific geographic locations were additional barriers to CC (Friedman et al., 2016; Solomon Michael et al., 2010).

Organizations can facilitate CC by engaging, training, and educating staff on the need, and importance of CC as well as the skills required for it (Berry et al., 2011; Elertson, 2017). CC is best enabled in healthcare settings that have designated staff who have developed meaningful relationships with other staff members, community providers, and patient representatives such as family, parents, and caregivers (Berry et al., 2011; Elertson, 2017; Schneiderman, 2005, 2008; Tschudy et al., 2016). Studies conducted found in-person communication established supportive relationships that were salient for CC (Dudley & Chapman, 2016; Edwards, 2013).

Care Coordination in Child Welfare

In a systematic review of 101 articles, child welfare was inconsistent and non-adhering to recommend health services for children in FC (Deans et al., 2015). National standards specific to child welfare are needed to inform lawmakers about the gaps in care that should be addressed to improve children's health outcomes (Deans et al., 2015; Elertson, 2017; Schneiderman et al., 2012). Child welfare needs a structure and policies that ensure PHNs and CGs are a part of the CC team to assist in ensuring a child receives a health assessment and services when needed (Sakai, 2014; Schneiderman, 2008; Szilagyi, 2015).

Collaboration

Interprofessional collaboration is defined as practitioners from different disciplines working together with the patient on common goals to deliver coordinated care (Clancy, Gressnes, & Svensson, 2013; Ketcherside, Rhodes, Powelson, Cox, & Parker, 2017; Rose, 2011). Collaboration among different professions is at the forefront of CC and plays an integral role in the future of delivering safe and quality healthcare

(Tomasik J, 2015). However, professional relationship issues can often lead to mistrust, communication, and job dissatisfaction (Costello & Thompson, 2015; Gould et al., 2015; Lalayants, 2013; Rose, 2011). Challenges to professional collaboration include lack of time to collaborate, lack of communication, and lack of committed staff. Effective collaboration is the result of having and using appropriate communication skills, a team approach attitude, trust, and respect for various professionals and non-professionals such as family members and CG (Dunworth & Kirwan, 2012; Ketcherside et al., 2017; Selleck et al., 2017).

Collaboration in child welfare involves the child/adolescent, SWs, PHNs, HCPs, and the CGs (Lalayants, 2012; Schneiderman, 2008). The collaborative focus is on the working relationships between the child welfare professionals with HCPs and CGs (Hood et al., 2017). To prevent adverse outcomes, the PHN, HCPs, and CG must work closely together with children who have complex medical conditions. Because a child's health status can rapidly decline, close collaboration between CGs and PHNs is required for children who have newly diagnosed insulin-dependent diabetes, seizure disorder, or infants who are experiencing withdrawal symptoms from prenatal exposure to drugs (Schneiderman 2008; Schneiderman, 2012). The PHN provides child-specific health education to CGs and SWs. PHNs understand that the more equipped and well-informed the CG is, the better prepared they are in providing care to a child (Cooley, Thompson, & Wojciak, 2017; Schneiderman, 2008; 2012).

A significant challenge for HCPs is receiving incomplete or limited health information on

a child's immunization status or previous/current medications and allergies (Schneiderman, 2008, 2012; Szilagyi et al., 2015). All FC health records, which may include a child's health history and birth records from previous child welfare contact, must be provided to the HCP by the PHN or SW. The collaborative efforts of the PHN, SW, and CG are imperative to ensure the most accurate and comprehensive health history is given to the HCP (Elertson, 2017; Szilagyi et al., 2015, Schneiderman, 2008).

When SWs provide the PHN with a written court order indicating a child is in FC, the PHN is authorized to collaborate with HCPs on treatment plans and legally obtain health exam results (Elertson, 2017). The sharing of a child's health information allows the PHN to enter health exam results into the child welfare medical records system, thus demonstrating that the requirements have been met and a child's health exam is in compliance with LADCFS policy (Elterson, 2017; Schneiderman 2012; Szilagyi et al., 2015). Collaboration about a child's health needs is the responsibility of SWs but often requires the health expertise of the PHNs and HCPs and the cooperation of CGs. Overcoming collaboration issues in the Child Welfare System (CWS) means understanding and respecting the role and priorities of each person involved in providing care and services for children in FC (Rose, 2011).

Communication

Communication is a key component to successful collaboration. In today's healthcare environment, poor communication adversely affects the delivery of care by creating an atmosphere wherein mistakes are likely to occur (Woods, Jackson, Ziglar, & Alston, 2011). The importance of communication in health care varied throughout the literature with most studies focused on the value of information-sharing and personal

interactions (Costello & Thompson, 2015; Lalayants, 2013; Szilagyi et al., 2015). While phone and emails are ways to communicate, they were found to be inefficient when compared to face-to-face dialogue (Costello & Thompson, 2015).

Communication among various disciplines can be enhanced by frequent in-person interaction between disciplines, confidence in speaking to others, and comfort with the topic being discussed (Dudley et al., 2016; Edwards et al., 2013). In child welfare, building and nurturing a trusting relationship between nurses, SWs, and CGs can be developed and strengthened through making joint home and office visits, and by sharing medical records and client information (Clancy, Gressnes, & Svensson, 2013; Lalayants, 2013; Szilagyi et al., 2015). Successful collaboration and effective communication are the hallmarks of coordinated care.

Summary

Children entering FC have higher rates of unmet medical and dental needs than children residing with their biological parent (Turney & Wildeman, 2016). Children in FC should have health and dental assessments and care completed as outlined in child welfare guidelines and recommendations (Szilagyi et al., 2015). Studies varied on their recommendations regarding how to enhance CC among child welfare PHNs and SWs, and CGs and HCPs (Berry et al., 2011, Elertson, 2017, Schneiderman, 2008). Most studies focused on the need for effective communication and collaboration (Tomasik, 2015; Dunworth & Kirwan, 2012; Ketcherside et al., 2017). Changes in healthcare organizations are expecting CC to save cost on healthcare expenses and the delivery of efficient and quality care (ARHQ, 2018; Cady et al., 2014). Despite the barriers of time constraints, weak communication skills, and unclear professional roles, studies showed

improved patient experiences and health outcomes when CC activities were performed (Camicia et al., 2013; Connor et al., 2018; Deans et al., 2015, Litt & McCormick 2015; Tschudy et al., 2016).

Based on current evidence, the use of CC activities in delivering quality care can meet the health needs of children and improve patient satisfaction and health outcomes (Berry et al., 2011; Brustrom, Thibadeau, John, Liesmann, & Rose, 2012; Litt & McCormick, 2015). Studies suggested that PHNs acting as health advocates and coordinating a child's care with SWs and CGs increased the number of health exams children in FC will have completed (Janevic et al., 2016; Brustrom et al., 2012). Such findings from the literature review support the implementation of a PHN driven CC practice guideline for this DNP project.

METHODS

The aim of this performance improvement project was to enhance care coordination activity among FC PHNs and improve medical and dental compliance at LACDCFS Torrance and Compton offices. To ensure a firm understanding of CC in the child welfare system and the impact of collaboration and communication on CC, a literature review was completed using the academic databases, PubMed, Medline, CINAHL, EBSCO and AHQR website (Appendix A). Current information on CC, case management, child welfare system, child protective services and interprofessional collaboration was obtained. Ethical considerations were discussed and an evaluation plan was outlined, including the data measured and how it was evaluated. Finally, a timeline with components of the project's conceptual model was charted (Appendix B).

Project Design

This performance improvement project employed a mixed method design. A qualitative study using focus groups was done to assess PHN's and SW's perceptions on CC and a quantitative pre-post design was used to measure PHN's performance before and after the implementation of the PHN roles and responsibilities policy. When assessing the effectiveness of an intervention, a pre-post, or before and after, design allows the measurement of change in the coordination activities and compliance rates (Polit & Beck, 2017).

Operational Definitions

Child Welfare Public Health Nursing Program (CWPHNP): The public health nursing program within Los Angeles County, Department of Public Health, Children's

Medical Services Division, which oversees the public health nurses providing care to children in FC.

Los Angeles County Department of Children and Family Services (LACDCFS):

The Los Angeles County Department within the California State Child Welfare System where the CWPHNP public health nurses are co-located with social workers assigned to children in placement.

Care coordination (CC): The practice of facilitating the delivery of comprehensive health promotion, and chronic disease management using communications skills to develop connections among medical providers, families, and health professionals (Looman et al., 2013).

Setting and Participants

The performance improvement pilot project took place at the LACDCFS Torrance and Compton offices. There are currently 1,236 children from the Torrance office and 2,092 children from the Compton office who are in FC placement. Four PHNs from the Torrance office and four PHNs from the Compton office participated in the project. The project took place from December 1st, 2018 through March 1st, 2019. Eight CWPHNP PHNs utilized the developed revised PHN roles and responsibilities policy which outlined the PHN's CC activities while working with court-detained children and adolescents in the FC system. Because of their medical expertise, FC PHNs in child welfare are the most equipped and prepared to implement and follow the PHN practice policy and effectively communicate and collaborate with HCPs. The increase in the number of new PHNs in the Torrance and Compton office lead to more time being spent

on educating and training the PHNs on the developed and revised PHN roles and responsibilities policy and data collection in the fusion system.

Stakeholders

Nursing and CG stakeholders

The PHNs and CGs are stakeholders for this project. PHN supervisors and PHNs are health advocates who ensure children and adolescents receive health care during their stay in the FC system. The PHN supervisor provided PHN CC activity data pre-and post-intervention for review and analysis. As providers of daily care for children, CG play a key role in ensuring health appointments are scheduled and maintained, often providing transportation. It is less strain on caregivers to foster a healthy child and one whose medical and dental needs are met than a child with health issues that may require time consuming multiple trips to specialty providers and complex medical regimens.

Child Welfare Stakeholders

The stakeholders in child welfare consist of the regional administrators (RA), SW Supervisors, and SWs. RAs hold the top administrative position in LACDCFS offices. One of the responsibilities of the RAs is to achieve the department's goal of medical and dental exams compliance rate of 90% and above for all children in FC. The LACDCFS Research and Development Department gave approval for project leader to review the office's health exam compliance rates before, during, and after the implementation of the PHN practice policy. The SWs are stakeholder responsible for regularly consulting and communicating with the PHNs. It is necessary for the SWs to provide PHNs with medical records and health-related details of the children on their caseload. For a child to be

considered in compliance with their health exam, the PHNs must review and update the medical records on a child.

Ethical Considerations

The project proposal was submitted and Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was given from LACDPH (Appendix C), LACDCFS (Appendix D), and California State University Fullerton (Appendix E). This performance improvement project enabled PHNs to base their practice on evidence-based research and had a low risk of harm to PHNs and SWs. All PHNs and SWs participating in the focus groups received an informed written consent. Any data extracted remains confidential and did not include any identifying information. The participation of PHNs in this project was voluntary. Participants did not receive any incentive for participating in the project.

Recruitment and Intervention Procedures

After the proposed project was presented to stakeholders and IRB approval was granted, the project leader recruited PHNs and SWs from the Compton and Torrance LACDCFS offices to participate in a focus group via verbal request, email, and posted flyers (Appendix F). A group with SWs was held in the Torrance office and one in the Compton office. A separate focus group was held in the Compton office for both Torrance and Compton PHNs. Participation in the focus group and this DNP project was voluntary. All participants received a project description and written consent to sign (Appendix G). The project leader moderated the focus groups. The participants were audio-recorded with permission, and the project team lead took notes. A questionnaire guided the group discussion which focused on perceptions of CC, challenges and barriers to CC, and quality improvement strategies (Appendix H). The evidence from the

literature review and the data from the focus groups were used, in conjunction with CWPHPN education department content experts, to revise the department's PHN Roles and Responsibilities Practice Policy. The DPH CWPHPN management team reviewed and approved the newly revised policy for use in this DNP project (Appendix I).

The project leader developed educational materials (Appendix J) for training participating PHNs and conducted 90-minute training sessions in each of the participating offices. In addition, one make-up training session was provided. As part of the training, the PHNs received a copy of the revised practice guideline in addition to training power point handouts. Implementation of the revised PHN practice policy started December 1st, 2018 and ended March 1st, 2019.

Measurement and Data Collection

The project PHNs documented their work activities into the LACDPH foster care program data system referred to as Fusion. The measurements used to assess PHN CC activities included consultations, communications, and health assessments (Appendix K). The compliance rates are the evidence to the number of children who completed comprehensive medical, and dental exams. This information is gathered from the LACDCFS internal electronic system, the site; *Statistic & Information Transmitted Everyday*. The compliance rates for medical and dental examinations in the Torrance and Compton offices were collected for three months following the implementation of the policy and its associated PHN education. These data were compared to the data for the same months in 2017 and 2018.

Data Analysis

The recordings of the data were transcribed, evaluated and categorized by two independent reviewers to ensure reliability. Content analysis was performed following the procedures outlined by Hsieh and Shannon (2005). This type of analysis used a systematic approach to identifying recurring themes. The relevant data in the text were coded and categorized, with emerging themes discovered. For validity, the themes identified at the manifest level (directly recognizable in the information) were compared to that from the latent level (underlying the information). At the completion of the improvement project, the LACDPH fusion reports along with LACDCFS medical and dental compliance rates reports pre-and post-intervention were analyzed.

RESULTS

The aim of this project was to develop and implement a nursing practice guideline to enhance care coordination activities of public health nurses (PHN) to improve medical and dental compliance rates among children and youth in FC. The pre and post data of PHN care coordination activities from the time period of December 1st, 2017 to March 1st, 2018 and from December 1st, 2018 to March 1st, 2019 was evaluated to determine if the intervention was effective in improving the overall medical and dental compliance rates of LACDCFS, Compton and Torrance offices.

Qualitative Results

The SWs and PHNs who participated in this project were from the DCFS Compton and Torrance offices. However, the focus groups participants were separated by disciplines. The participants were asked questions to examine their viewpoints, perceptions, and understanding of CC and their role in CC. The discussion focused on three topic areas, perception CC, perceived challenges and barrier to CC and lastly, their recommended strategies to improve the quality of CC SW's, PHNs and CGs. The responses were evaluated using content analysis and themes emerged from the data.

Best Coordinator

The first area on perception of care coordination, two key themes emerged from the data: 1) *Best coordinator* of children's health needs, 2) *Communication*. The SWs felt the PHNs are best equipped to coordinate and manage the children's medical and dental needs because community providers and CGs see PHNs as the most knowledgeable person on the children health needs. The CSWs see the involvement of PHNs is necessary for meeting a child's health needs and the compliance requirements of

LADCFS. Some SWs want the PHNs to completely manage the medical and dental portion of a child's case. The SWs made the following quotes:

"Sometimes when we tell families to take the child to the dentist or the doctor, they feel like it is an order instead of us assisting them with maintaining their healthcare. So, when the nurse gets involved, that information is coming from a reliable and credible source that they trust, so they are more likely to follow through with whatever is necessary for the child."

"Medical and dental care should totally be given to the nurses" and "I do not feel adequate to review or understand the medical reports."

"I'm not an RN, and I didn't go to school to be one."

"It should not be the SW to track and adapt medical and dental....it should be the sole primary position for the nurse to gather that information."

In contrast, PHNs believe the frequent interaction that SWs have with each child and their biological family gives them a greater awareness and insight of a child's health need and therefore, SWs should continue as the child's case manager and collaborate with their assigned PHN as needed. The PHNs made the following comments:

"The SW is the center point, the person who's in charge of the entire picture."

"We have to rely on them to kind of help get the kids what they need."

"Like they say, they are the case managers."

"We are supposed to let them know what is going on with the child and they let us know what they see in the homes when they visit monthly and bring us back a complete medical record that we never get."

Communication

SWs and PHNs valued the theme communication. Both disciplines regarded communication as vital to building trusting relationships and successful CC. The PHNs responses included:

“Communication among PHNs, SWs, CG, Health Providers is key to appropriate, meaningful CC of children in foster care.”

“Face to face or in person communication leads to building a trusting and open relationship.”

“I have very good communication with my social workers, and they have it with me.”

“Joint home visit promotes the building and establishing a trusting/open relationship with CSW’s and CG.”

“When you go on a visit with SW, you form a bond and work better together.”

The SWs responses regarding communication varied among the two offices. Most SWs felt communication was effective in collaborating to ensure CC is completed. The SWs from both offices made the following comments:

“PHNs communicate to SWs on child issues via email or in person and provide recommendations.”

“PHNs are available for home visits and CFTs” and “PHNs are accessible when It’s not your assigned nurse, you get help.”

“PHNs communicate directly with CGs, I really appreciate that.”

“The community and caregivers see PHNs as helpers and healers, PHNs are able to have a better report with the families and caregivers, they listen to the PHN.”

There were a few SWs from the Torrance office who viewed the communication among staff differently and would like to see improvement in communication between themselves and their assigned PHN. Those SWs made these comments:

“When I request for the PHN you know by email can you come out with me, I need you to go to the home and assess the kid, nothing is ever done, no follow-up, no phone call, and I have to go to another PHN.”

“Often, from the PHN I work with, I’ll get a not so friendly email about what I didn’t have and what I needed.”

From the second topic area on the challenges and barriers to CC that may hinder the medical and dental exam compliance rate of children in FC, emerged three themes: 1) *Workload*, 2) *PHN policy*, 3) *Caregiver responsibility*.

Workload

The PHNs and SW recognized that increased workload places unmanageable pressure on both PHNs and CSWs. High caseloads can delay the coordination of children’s care and interfere with their wellbeing. One SW stated, *“Work overload for both is tremendous”* Other SWs shared these remarks:

“The movement in the office in the last 3-4 months, we have gained so many Supervising Children Social Worker, which means more new units, and for you guys (PHNs), to have to carry that additional load is not fair, and its inequity.”

“We can visibly see the PHNs with piled up medical folders on their desk.”

“The medical and dental exam reports are not updated and processed timely or before they become out of compliance due to nurses’ work overload.”

“We are pushed to the limit, and we are continuously told to operate in the fashion of the department, which is providing care and effective services.”

“Can’t provide caring/effective services if we don’t have the tools within the house to meet the demands of the staff.”

The PHNs expressed great concern regarding their caseload and their ability to provide effective care: PHNs comments included the following:

“Having a PHN ratio of one nurse for 350-450 kids is way too much.”

“Establishing a PHN ratio of one PHN to 2 SW units is required to provide monitoring and holistic care, and that is what really needs to happen in order for us to be able to do our jobs completely and effectively, and it actually make it meaningful.”

“There is a lot of SWs compared to the limited amount of PHNs.” “There is an increase in the number of SWs and Supervising SWs, but the number of PHNs have not increased.”

PHN Policy

The policy on expected role and expectations of the PHN was a theme that emerged from the PHN focus group. Many of the PHNs shared the same sentiments regarding the lack of a clearly defined policy on the PHN role and responsibilities within the child welfare system and a need for education and training on the policy. The PHNs made the following comments:

“The PHN policy should be simplified, more specific and clearer.”

“Our roles and responsibility policy is very general.”

“There is a lack of uniformity in the policy from office to office.”

“There are not enough PHN Supervisor to assist with understanding the policy.”

Caregiver Responsibility

Caregivers whether foster parents or relatives are a vital part of the team. They are essential to CC but were viewed by staff as having no legal accountability for a child’s health care needs not being met. The lack of caregiver’s accountability for taking children and youth to their health exam appointments was an overarching theme for both PHNs and CSWs. Most of the time, it is the CGs who schedule a child’s exam and are responsible for taking them to that medical or dental appointment. PHNs and SWs feel many CGs are nonchalant and non-compliant with taking children to receive preventive care, even when informed to do so by the SW or the PHN. It was also stated that when CG do attend the child’s appointment, they do not have the provider complete the necessary exam report documentation required by DCFS. There may be a need for more CG oversight and accountability by LACDCFS. The staff made the following comments during the focus group discussion:

“Court does not hold the CG accountable at all,” and “Not enough accountability for CG.”

“CG need to be more responsible for the kid’s health requirements.”

“Relative CG are the worst, and harder to deal with.”

“CG only become responsible when the child’s care deals with CG getting increased funding” and “CG are more receptive if it is related to money; they are very, very, responsive.”

The last themes emerged from the focus groups data were on strategies that could improve CC and the quality of care through 1) *System and Process Changes*, and 2)

Utilization of Intermediate Clerks (ITCs) and Human Service Aids (HSAs) in a different way.

System and Process Changes

The SWs and PHNs discussed the system and process changes that can be made by their respective departments to improve the ability of CC by PHNs and SWs collaboratively, increase the number of medical and dental exam updated, and the office medical and dental compliance rates. The SW's provided the following recommendations:

"The creation of a specialized SW unit to handle all the medical and dental care of children; those SW could pass the medical folder on to the nurse."

"I am solution focused; the remedy is we need a unit to be in the middle between the us and the PHN."

"The PHN can make the appointments with or for the CGs."

"There should be one PHN for every two units of CSWs."

The recommendations offered by the PHNs included:

"There must be an established PHN to child ratio established" and "Hire more PHNs to adequately staff the offices."

"I've sent an email to the supervising social workers and asked them if I can attend (unit meeting) and I won't get a response. I have still not attended a unit meeting. I've even walked to her cubicle and asked her, hey, I sent emails and introduced myself and said oh please if I can attend the next unit meeting and she said yes, but still has not followed through."

“The medical and dental forms need to be updated to include the CHDP information needed,” and “We can adopt the form Orange County’s DCFS uses.”

“Add CWS/CMS to the new PHN hire training.”

“Clearer PHN policies and more PHN training.”

“We need access to the ORCHID database.”

Different Utilization of Intermediate Typist Clerk (ITC) and Human Service Aid (HSA)

While focus groups were held separately, both the PHNs and SWs agreed that changes in the role and job duties of the ITCs and HSAs are needed. Both supportive staff members could be trained to better assist the PHNs and CSWs, not only in the coordination of a child’s care but also to ensure health exam reports are completed and provided to both the PHNs and SWs. The suggestions included:

“Send HSA to the medical offices to pick up the health exam reports from providers and CGs.”

“Train the ITC’s to better assist the SWs.” “ITCs can make copies of exams reports and give them to the CSW for their court reports, and to the PHNs to review and enter.”

“HSAs or ITCs can send letters to the families when a child is due for an exam.”

“ITCs can help the SWs with their filing of documents into the proper child files, request records and send faxes.”

The results of the focus groups were taken into consideration and used to inform the revisions on the current PHN roles and responsibilities policy and procedure practice guideline. This new revised policy (Appendix I) gives the PHNs more authority to be proactive in following up or coordinating the care of a child or youth who require

preventive health exams. The participating PHNs were educated and trained on the revised policy (Appendix I).

Quantitative Results

The eight PHNs from the LADCFS Compton and Torrance office participated in the DNP project and entered their care coordination activities into the CWPHNP's data collection system weekly. The number of PHN consults, communication activities, and medical and dental exam updated by each PHN are the process measures analyzed weekly and/or monthly. The project leader obtained the medical and dental compliance rates from the LACDCFS data management system; the SITE. The project results were compared to the outcomes during the same time period from the previous year and the month before project implementation. The stratification of data by time periods was done to assist with gaining understanding of the causal mechanism of a change.

PHN to Child Ratio

During the pre-implementation period of 2017, there was 1,663 court detained children and youth placed in foster care and assigned to the LACDCFS Compton office and one PHN for every 277 of those children. In 2018, there were 1,844 detained children assigned to the Compton office with one PHN for every 461 children. In 2017, the LACDCFS Torrance office had 1,131 foster children in placement with one PHN for every 377 children. This ratio is compared to the third quarter of 2018, where 1,115 children in FC were assigned to the Torrance office which meant one PHN for every 278 children.

Figure 4. PHN to child ratio in quarter 3, 2017 and quarter 3, 2018.

Data Improvement Charts

In general, improvement projects are completed to test, adapt, implement, and make changes in a process or system through a pre-and post-test design (Provost & Murray, 2011). In improvement projects, performance is evaluated rather than testing a hypothesis. A Shewhart control (c) chart is a graph of data with an average and sigma lines that determines process stability. It is best to graphically display quality improvement project results on a c chart where measurement is made over time (Provost & Murray, 2011). The c chart is a statistical tool used to distinguish between the types of variation seen in a measure. The variation can be from a common cause which is the natural variation that exist in any process or because of a special cause. A special cause is something that arises in the process because of a specific circumstance or something out of the ordinary such as an implemented intervention (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Control charts include a center line (CL) which is the mean of the total data points on a control chart, an upper control limit (UCL), and a lower control limit (LCL) that are

computed from sigma statistical theory (Provost & Murray, 2011). The zones created by the 3 sigma lines and stability rules are used to analyze data and identify special causes that may indicate an improvement in a process after an intervention is introduced. Special cause variation can be identified by of a single data point above the UL or below the LL, eight or more data points in a row above or below the CL, or six consecutive points going in an upward or downward trend. The data points on the chart that are blue indicate a common cause and the red data points indicate a variation change based on the Shewhart chart rules. The number of PHNs consults and communication activities are measurements of quantitative attribute count data that is best displayed on a c chart. Therefore, a control (c) chart and bar graphs were created by QI Macros SPC software and used to display the PHNs consult and communication results.

PHN Consultations

The pre-implementation time of 2017 to 2018 was compared to the same months in 2018 and 2019 post-implementation. The total number of consultations completed weekly and monthly for each project office is presented. The pre-implementation control chart in Compton shows multiple data points that are above the UL 91.9 and below the LL 42.7 this chart displayed special cause variations due to an unstable process. This instability pre-implementation resulted from PHNs not entering their consult data into the Fusion data collection system on a weekly basis. The average consults completed during this time period is 67.3 consults. At the end of this time period, there is a noted special cause variation data point of 138. This was due to an increased number of consultations completed and entered by Compton PHNs. Post-implementation, the Compton office displayed a data point of 29 below the LL of 38.5. This signaled a special cause variation

due to the introduction of the new PHN policy and procedure guideline into the process. Common cause variation is noted throughout the rest of the project due to a more stable process of PHNs entering the Fusion data weekly.

Figure 5. Compton PHN consults from 12/2017 to 3/2018 and 12/2018 to 3/2019

The pre-implementation average consults in Torrance was 44.2 a month. The Torrance control chart showed multiple data points below the LCL of 24.2 which indicated special cause variation throughout most of the weeks. The unstable process was due to inconsistent documentation of the PHNs. The post-implementation results from the Torrance office displayed data points -2 sigma to +2 sigma from the CL of 64.2 which demonstrates common cause variation indicating a stable process of data being entered by PHNs and the introduction of the revised PHN practice guideline. As the project weeks continued, the number of consultations completed where at or above the CL 64.2 hitting with a high point of the UCL of 88.2.

Figure 6. Torrance PHN consults from 12/2017 to 3/2018 and 12/2018 to 3/2019.

The PHN consult bar graph displayed the total number of monthly consults completed by Compton and Torrance PHNs. Compton office PHNs completed a increased number of consults in 2017-2018 than in the same months of 2018-2019. This was possibly due to the office being fully staffed. However, one-month pre-implementation, there was 198 consults completed November 2018. The number of consults increased to 285 and 273 by the second and third-month respectively post implmnetation of the revised PHN practice guideline. The Torrance off PHNs completed more consults in 2017 and 2018 compared to the same previous months. The PHNs completed 210 consults November 2018 pre-implementation and increased to 313 consults completed in the last month of the project February 2019. of completed consults by end of the project.

Figure 7. The Torrane and Compton office monthly number of PHN consults completed.

Communication

The PHNs' communication activity is essential in the performance of CC. The pre-implementation control chart from the Compton and Torrance office in 2017 and 2018 displayed random process variation of special cause due to the inconsistency of PHNs documented communication data into Fusion. The data points are above UCL and below the LCL. The post-implementation in Compton displayed a special cause variation in week one with a data point of 25 that is below the LL of 40.3 due to start of the implemented revised practice guideline. During week four of the project in Compton, there was common cause variation close to the LCL, in which additional training was provided to the project PHNs. Common cause variation was displayed in the remainder of the project weeks. There was special cause variation at the start of the project in the Torrance office. Week one's data point was 38 which was below the LCL of 57, indicating the implementation of the practice guideline. Special cause variation was noted in week five of the project due to lack of knowledge regarding the Fusion collection

system. After additional training was provided, there was an increase in data points indicating process stabilization. There was a special cause variation noted in the last week of the process with a data point at the UCL of the CL of 112.

Figure 8. Number of communication activities completed by Compton office PHNs.

Figure 9. Number of communication activities completed by Torrance office PHNs.

The monthly communication activity increased in both offices. In Compton, the monthly communications for both time periods were consistent with each other. The pre-

implementation communication activity increased from 184 in November 2018 to 276 after the first month and to 315 after the second month of the project. However, it slightly decreased to 233 by end of the project. The Torrance office PHNs demonstrated an increase in their communication activities in 2018 and 2019 when compared to the previous time period of 2017 and 2018. The PHNs had 268 monthly communication activities in November 2018 prior to implementation that increased to 384 after the second month, and 369 for February 2019.

Figure 10. Number of monthly communication activities by Compton and Torrance office PHNs.

Medical Exams Updated by PHN

From the Fusion data collected, the number of medical exams entered during the two time periods are comparable. Pre-implementation medical exams reviewed and entered were compared to post-implementation results. Compton PHNs completed more exams post implementation of the PHN roles and responsibility policy. In November

2018, one month before commencing the revised policy, Compton had 118 exams entered. During the project, there were 137 medical exams entered, after the second month, 144 were entered and after the third month 131 medical exams were entered by the PHNs. The PHNs in Compton demonstrated an increase in the number medical exams they completed and entered every month. The Compton PHNs entered more exams from November 2018 through February 2019 with less PHNs than the time period of November 2017 through January 2018. The Torrance office, PHNs entered 41 medical exams in November 2018 which increased to 64 in December 2018 and more than doubled to 96 in the final project month February 2019.

Figure 11. Number of medical exams entered by Compton and Torrance office PHNs.

Dental Exams Updated by PHN

Dental exams entered by PHNs between pre-and post-policy change, there were 72 dental exams updated in November 2018 by Compton PHNs which increased the next month to 80, decreased to 78 exams in January 2019, and ended with 71 dental exams

entered during the month of February 2019. In addition, the Compton office PHN lacked two PHNs, yet, they were consistent in the number of dental exams entered from the pre-implementation time period of this project. The Torrance office showed similar result in the number dental exams entered during both time periods. However, there were small increases in dental exams entered each month. Post- implementation data showed the number of dental exams entered went from 27 in November 2018 to 49 in February 2019.

Figure 12. Number of dental exams entered by Compton and Torrance office PHNs.

DCFS Medical/Dental Compliance Rates

Prior to this project, the average medical compliance rate in the Compton and Torrance offices was 52% and 56%, and the dental compliance was 34% and 29% respectively. After the second month of the project, in Compton, the medical compliance rates increased by 5% from 56% to 61%, but there was a decrease in dental compliance rates from 34% to 30%. The Torrance office medical exam compliance rate increased by 5% from 52% to 57% but showed a decrease by the end of the project to 55%. There was

a decrease in dental exam compliance rate from 29% to 27% and to 24% by the end of the project. At the conclusion of this project on March 1st, 2019, LACDCFS's average medical and dental compliance rate was 62% for medical compliance and 37% dental compliance.

Figure 13. LACDCFS Compton medical and dental compliance rates.

Figure 14. LACDCFS Torrance medical and dental compliance rates.

DISCUSSION

Children and youth placed in foster care require initial medical and dental exams within thirty days. At the inception of this project, the Compton office had a compliance rates of 57% medical and 28% dental and Torrance had a medical compliance rate of 44%, and dental rate of 18%. After the first month of the implementation of the new PHN practice policy and procedure, Compton's medical and dental compliance rates were 58% medical and 34% dental. Torrance's compliance rates were medical 51% and dental 26%. The project goal was to increase the compliance rates. The goal of LACDCFS is to have 90% compliance in children completing their required health assessments. However, it takes collective collaboration and coordination for those health assessments to get completed. PHNs are to consult with SWs when they become aware of a child who needs preventive exams, follow-up care, or immediate attention. However, because of identified barriers, such as staffing shortage and the lack of communication between PHNs and SWs, that does not always occur. PHNs who wait on the SWs to consult with them before taking action may cause a delay in CC resulting in fragmented and less than optimal care for FC children and youth. According to Clancy et al. (2015, p. 666), To guard against territorial thinking, child welfare agencies should promote open communication and collaborative relationships among staff, caregivers, and healthcare providers that is guided by integrity and mutual respect.

Review of Framework as Applied to Project

The selected Public Health Nursing Practice Model and PRECEDE-PROCEED Model adapted from (Smith & Bazini-Barakat, 2003; Green & Kreuter, 1999) was the framework applied to this DNP project. The health outcome goal of every child and

youth placed in the FC system will have a comprehensive health exam completed was identified in phase one of the PRECEDE section of the model. In phase four through the education and organization assessment, the lack of CC and knowledge of the PHN and SW roles, different priorities of PHNs and SWs, and unstable FC placement for children are the predisposing factors identified as inhibiting effective CC and were considered through the implementation of this project. The enabling factors included Medi Cal insurance for each child and access to designated medical hub clinics.

As part of phase five, the administrative and policy assessment of the PPM, the current CWPHPN roles and responsibility policy was reviewed. The current literature and results of the focus groups were taken into consideration and with the assistance of the PHN program education team, revisions on the current PHN roles and responsibilities policy and procedure practice guideline was completed. The following interventions were added to the existing policy:

- 1) **Consultation and Assessment:** Review the DCFS Statistics and Information Transmitted Everyday (SITE) monthly for assigned FC children and youth who are out of DCFS medical and dental compliance according to Bright Futures and American Academy of Pediatrics Recommendations for preventive pediatric health care.

Responsibilities include efforts to:

- Identify children who require current medical or dental examination.
- Provide the report to the assigned CSW/SCSW.
- Review child's medical file for completed medical/dental exam reports/records.

- 2) **Collaboration and Evaluation:** Collaborate with assigned CSW to determine and discuss appropriate plan required to bring child's health exams into compliance.
- 3) **Coordination of Services:** Contact and coordinate with caregiver/resource family to schedule required medical and dental exams and document appointment location, date, and time in CWS/CMS as per PHN Documentation Policy.
- 4) **Participation:** Participate in SCSW unit and/or ARA section meetings to educate DCFS on the role of PHNs, various health topics, current pertinent nursing policies/procedures.

The revised practice policy was reviewed and approved by the program manager. The project's participating PHNs were trained on the revised policy. The PHNs were open to the new policy, yet there were several inquiries and concerns such as implementing a proactive policy which includes PHN tracking medical and dental compliance rates monthly and then requesting the medical file for each child who is out of compliance may be unrealistic for the PHN to complete during this PHN shortage. The PHNs felt this policy may increase an already unmanageable and high caseload. The PHNs working in the Compton office had an increase caseload due to lacking two full-time PHNs. Currently, there is one PHN for 471 children placed in out of home care in the Compton office compared to the previous time period when the ratio was one PHN for 277 children. The Torrance office received two new PHNs at the start of this project who are still learning their foundational role.

The organization policies and system process reviewed in Phase 5 of the PPM revealed the demands of a SW's mixed responsibilities. The SWs priority is for every

child in foster care to have a safe placement and environment to reside, free from physical, emotional or sexual abuse. Along with that responsibility, SWs must ensure each child is enrolled in an appropriate educational setting and receiving mandatory well child preventive health assessments. There would be an advantage for Los Angeles Departments of Public Health, Health Services, and Children and Family Services to restructure the role of PHNs working in LACDCFS. These PHN could work and function as health care managers having full access to medical files, records, and laboratory results of children in foster care. This health care manager PHN could streamline their activities to be more efficient; eliminating wasted time and duplicating nursing interventions and documentation.

As the project moved forward through the PROCEED section of the PPM, the project was implemented from December 1st, 2018 to March 1st, 2019. The application of the project launched with PHNs reviewing the SITE health compliance reports which allowed each PHN to identify every child on their caseload who did not have a documented preventive medical or dental exam. The PHNs then initiated a consult with the SW to share the compliance report with and request the child's medical file. Once the PHN had access to the child's medical file, they were able to determine if a current health report was available and if not, they began to communicate back with the SWs, and with the child's CG, and HCP to obtain the health information or to ensure the child was scheduled for the appropriate medical and/or dental appointment.

During phase seven, process evaluation was completed. In weeks two and three of implementation, it became apparent, that PHNs were not inputting their work activities and information into the Fusion data collection system consistently. The consult control

charts demonstrate these variations in the process. The project leader provided one on one additional training to the new PHNs in both offices. The quantitative results were reviewed in phase eight of the PPM to evaluate its impact on CC. The weekly communication run charts (Figures 8 and 9) and monthly graphs (Figure 10) confirmed that PHNs increased their performance in the number of communication activities they completed regarding the needs and/or the coordination of a child's care. These process measures showed an increase in PHN contact with SWs, CGs, and community health providers was the expected outcome from implementing the revised PHN policy. The graphs (Figures 10 and 11) showed an increase in the number of medical and dental exams entered by PHNs in both offices. The run chart data should continue to be collected for another three months to ensure the increase in PHN performance is sustained. This increase showed a statistical change despite the small impact on the medical compliance goals of the department.

In the final phase of the PPM, the outcome measure of this project was evaluated. The compliance rates pre-post implementation were reviewed (Figures 13 and 14). The medical exam compliance rate in Compton increased by 4%. It is expected this rate will increase more when the office is fully staffed with the additional two full time nurses. Torrance showed a 2% increase in the medical compliance rate. It is anticipated the rate will increase as the new PHNs become more comfortable and efficient in their role as a PHN and a child advocate. Both offices experienced a decrease in their respective dental compliance rates (Figures 13 and 14) over the time period of this project. Compton's dental rate remains in the 20-percentile and Torrance in the 30-percentile range. The reason for this decrease requires further investigation.

The PHNs exerted great effort in their performance in attempting to achieve the project's goal of increasing the compliance rates. The department's current goal of a 90% compliance rate is not currently met by any of their offices. It is necessary to have a proper understanding of the current situation before setting goals (Filip, 2010). Having small attainable goals raises the confidence and enhances the internal motivation of staff (Stratton, 2005; Filip, 2010). Creating short-term and long-term goals is beneficial because attaining the short-term goals can identify enabling resources and support systems to achieve the longer-term goals (Filip, 2010). Another benefit is that short-term goals allow for frequent process evaluation to assess if the practice policy is being implemented as expected and if not, changes can be made to redirect the process in the right direction. PHNs may feel encouraged when they are kept informed on their progress. If PHNs weekly Fusion stats are low, it may compel them to work harder to reach the office compliance goals.

Public Health Nurses and Social Worker Care Coordination Insights

The focus groups results yielded rich information on PHNs and SWs perception and challenges to CC, and strategies they felt would improve CC and interdisciplinary collaboration. A PHN's priority is the health and well-being of a child while SW's priorities are child safety. This difference in priorities was discussed with the project PHNs so they could have a better understanding of the role of SWs and why children completing medical and dental exams may not be a SW's top priority. While PHNs and SWs differ as to who should be the lead coordinator, they both recognize communication is a key factor in coordinating a child's care as well as building trust with one another.

The new PHN practice policy provides PHNs with an intervention to contact and communicate directly with each child's caregiver and healthcare provider in the pursuit of providing best practice care. SWs are thankful when PHN communicate directly with the CG to obtain information on a child. Findings from this study regarding the importance and value of interprofessional communication to CC is consistent with literature studies reporting effective communication as a trademark of providing safe and effective patient care. Interdisciplinary communication and collaboration to coordinate care is facilitated by defined roles and responsibilities and communication (Dudley & Chapman, 2016). Inadequate communication has been considered one of the leading causes of medical errors and adverse events in health care (Hackett & Johnson, 2018). Collaboration in health care systems must be an organizational goal, with effective communication driving safe patient care

High caseloads were a great concern for both PHNs and SWs. The SWs recognize that the understaffing of PHNs in the Compton office and the presence of new PHNs in the Torrance office impacts the number of medical and dental exams updated and rendered compliant. PHN staffing should allow for one PHN for every 200 children according to the State of California Department of Health Services Memorandum of Understanding (California Department of Health Services, 2015). PHNs having high caseloads made it difficult for them to consistently implement the revised PHN roles and responsibility policy evident by the control charts demonstrating an inconsistent and unstable process of PHNs inputting their completed work into Fusion. SWs felt their high caseloads often prevent them from consulting with and providing PHNs with the child's medical file containing the necessary completed medical and dental reports. PHNs

expend a good amount of their work time providing CC to meet the needs of children and their families. One study conducted on Utah's child welfare system showed that each child placed in foster care is assigned a nurse manager at a ratio of one nurse per 100 children (Zlotnik, Wilson, Scribner, Wood, & Noonan, 2015). In order to provide quality competent care to their assigned FC child, PHNs and SWs need manageable caseloads.

SWs requested additional tools such as software applications that could provide them with reminders or alerts when a child is due or past due for a health assessment. In addition, a secure and appropriate method of making copies or transmitting a copy of a child's health report during home or community visits to a child and caregiver. CSWs felt these additional steps would support their work and the management of their caseloads. The PHNs and SW's agreed the clerical staff and human service aids could assist with CC by obtaining the children's medical and dental documentation from the CG or HCP and submitting the entire medical file to the nurse expediently. They could also send letters to the CG's home, informing them of when their child is due for an annual health assessment. The more realistic PHN and SW caseloads are and the more assistance they have, PHNs and CSW can provide safer environments, comprehensive healthcare to children and youth in FC, and move closer to the department's health assessments compliance goal of 90%.

The literature supports the views expressed by the PHNs and SWs, patients have better experiences and health outcomes as a result of CC (Brustrom et al., 2012; Cady et al., 2014; Connor, 2018; Janevic et al., 2016; Schultz, Pineda, Lonhart, Davies, & McDonald, 2013). The lack of time, inadequate communication skills of staff members, organizational systems and policies, and unclear professional roles were identified as the

most frequent barriers to CC (Camicia et al., 2013; Deans et al., 2015; Tschudy et al., 2016). Most studies focused on the impact of collaboration and the importance of effective communication. Studies found in-person communication established supportive relationships that were salient have for CC (Dudley & Chapman, 2016; Edwards, 2013). Brustrom et al., (2012) suggests adequate staffing and staff support are crucial to effective implementation of CC. Scholarly literature supports the findings in this DNP project on the need for effective communication, collaborative work by PHNs and SWs, practicable caseloads and the restructuring of some system challenges such as records access, ancillary staff resource. In addition, role clarity for PHNs and SWs is a must for LACDCFS to provide optimal safe care for children and youth in foster care.

Limitations

The focus groups offered a better understanding of CC in child welfare and the collaboration between PHNs and SWs. In addition, the impact of a proactive PHN practice policy yielded positive results in the improvement of PHNs consultation and communication activities. However, this project is not without limitations. The purposive sampling for the focus group was aimed to include participants from only the Compton and Torrance offices. Therefore, the qualitative results have limited generalizability and may indicate potential response bias. Participants of the focus group are in office where there is a shortage of nurses which may not exist for all the other 17 department offices. Each department office has their own set of issues and concerns. There are noted difference within the two projects offices, and they vary in the amount of PHN and SW interaction, communication, and care coordination. Utilizing participants from the other LACDCFS offices can provide a larger sample size which could provide greater insight

as to where and why other issues exist and identify gaps in knowledge for future education and training. In general, more data from a larger sample size leads to more information and better precision of results (Provost & Murray, 2011). Implementing this performance improvement project in offices where PHN staffing was an issue limited the full scope of this project and may have affected the quantitative results. Without adequate nursing staff, there was a high PHN/child ratio which limited the evaluation and impact of the revised guideline on increasing the health assessment compliance rates. Another limitation was the PHN's lack of direct access to a child's medical file which delayed comprehensive assessment and review of a child's health needs.

Recommendations

- 1) Because, the revised policy did not address the system barriers and challenges regarding children's medical files, it is recommended the PHNs have more authority and unfettered access to medical records so they may perform their job duties more efficiently and expediently.
- 2) Because office work, such as obtaining records and entering data take PHNs away from care coordination, it is recommended that intermediate technical clerks and human service aids receive additional training to appropriately assist SWs and PHNs with care coordination activities that can be delegated to these staff.
- 3) Because ongoing communication is critical in care coordination, it is recommended
 - a) PHNs should be invited and attend Supervising SW unit meetings in to provide the unit with their monthly compliance rates, health updates and education and discuss any areas of concern.

- b) A quarterly meeting should be held with child welfare staff, PHNs, community providers and caregivers.

Conclusion

The overall success of this DNP project relied on the openness and receptiveness of PHNs to use the interventions in the revised roles and responsibility policy to communicate and advocate for children. PHNs can enhance CC activities by overcoming the identified barriers such as the lack of time and increase workload. Despite department process and system issues and challenges, PHNs who take a proactive role as a child health advocate can be influential in ensuring children and youth placed in the foster care received preventive healthcare. Over the project months, the PHNs increased the number of consultations, communication activities completed, and health assessments entered to improve medical compliance rates. The targeted increase in medical and dental compliance had mixed results due to ongoing system issues working across agency lines that prohibited PHN ready access to the records of the children they served and to the unduly large caseload that were present during the project period. Nevertheless, the revised PHN Roles and Responsibilities policy and the associated training did have a positive impact on the number of PHN consultation, communication and record entries of medical and dental examinations. This is an encouraging impact on nurses' activities in care coordination and it is anticipated that this change will have a greater impact when key system issues, such as nurse-foster child ratio, ready access to case records, and auxiliary staff clerical support.

Dissemination

This DNP project was presented at the April 2019 Western Institute of Nursing Conference in San Diego, California (Appendix L) and at the Los Angeles County, Department of Public Health, Nursing Practice Conference in May 2019 (Appendix M).

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APPENDIX A
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Evidence Table 1

Care Coordination in Child Welfare

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
Describe effectiveness of health education for FC case managers & medical compliance rates (Elertson, 2017)	Quantitative 4-month experimental study IV: Child health education sessions & development of state IT health report system DV: Medical exam compliance rate	Case mangers/SW (N = 197) 94% of staff Milwaukee, Wisconsin Child Welfare System	Health exam completion compliance rates	Medical exam compliance increased each month, for the total 4 months of pilot (P = .004) Days from exam to completion of documentation decreased (P = .006)	Limitations: Case Mangers/SW perception of importance of completing exam was not measured Lacks generalizability Conclusion: Edu. & performance response increased med exam compliance rate Notes: Case manager/SW responded to rationale of importance of med exam completion for FC children, compliance rates improved

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
Examine how PHNs view CWS Organization & its effect on PHNs providing case management/CC (Schneiderman, 2005)	Qualitative Descriptive study	Purposive sampling of PHNs & SW (N = 10) Child Welfare System		PHNs-health is a part of safety, child advocates, work rewarding, desire to make impact, CC to meet child's need Stressful work environment d/t BOS & media scrutiny, increase workloads, little power, SWs unaware of PH role, waiting for consult from SW CWS large system makes change difficult	Limitations: Sm. sample size, non-randomized, limits generalizability Conclusion: Org. obstacle to access child & medical records, limits PHN ability for CC CC Notes: Nurse need to show their valuable to the org., be mindful & pragmatic about their role/power in CWS PHN lack power in CWS to make an org. change in a way they can increase their CC abilities
Describe Nurses' view on role of health case manager in FC (Schneiderman, 2008)	Qualitative descriptive study	Purposive sample PHN (N = 8) at LACDCFS	Interviews Motivation to provide holist care CC for preventive services	PHNs want children to have comprehensive care uninterrupted by placement changes, remove the CWS barriers to CC, for HC to be a part of SW safety plan, be part of the CW care team	Limitations: Small sample size, lacks generalizability Study did not, include HCP role, No measure PHNs CC on health outcomes

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
				SW case manager limits PHN access to child's MR Lack of communication b/t CWS & medical providers & CC	Conclusion: PHN limited to work to full scope of practice
Identify potential quality measures for healthcare of children in FC (Deans et al., 2015)	Integrative review	Inclusion: FC guidelines, recommendations, reviews, web sites Exclusion: Adults	Domains: Entry & exit FC exams, ongoing physical, mental, trauma care, placement changes with reassessment & CC	Professional guidelines in place for children in FC health, but lacks compliance Evidence indicates high variability, low compliance with guidelines & Recommendations	Limitations: Large data pool may not show individualized child needs Conclusion: National measures are needed to reveal the gap in care for CWS & law makers Notes: Gaps in care require CC & planning
Explore the observations of FP & CC to meet child's health needs (Schneiderman et al., 2012)	Qualitative study	Purposive sample FP (n = 25), different geographic regions, English & Spanish speaking Los Angeles, Ca.	Semi structure interviews Factors that helped with accessing HC View on child's health status Knowledge of pediatric health conditions	Advocacy, determination & resourceful helped get needed HC Capable to complete exams & understand home care instructions Relied on & received support from family, friends & agencies more than DCFS	Limitations: Lacks generalizability, non-random sample Conclusion: -Lack of stability & continuous care -Medical home for continuity care -Nurse needed for CC

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
			Amount of DCFS support with CC	Challenges in getting specialty care & insurance issues	<p>Notes: FP are strong leaders in meeting children's HC needs</p> <p>Improving HC access & outcomes includes the FP as part of the CW team</p>

Evidence Table 2

Care Coordination in Other Pediatric Settings

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
<p>To explore care coordination (CC) in spina bifida (SB) clinics (Brustrom et al., 2012)</p>	Qualitative study	<p>Clinic Staff (N=43)</p> <p>Focus groups conducted (N=38) with CG</p> <p>7 SB clinics in the US from: -2 Midwest -2 Southern -2 East coast -1 Pacific region</p>	<p>Semi structured interviews</p> <p>Focus groups with caregivers</p> <p>Characterize methods & practices of CC</p> <p>Examine effectiveness, benefits, obstacles, and enablers of CC</p>	<p>Holistic approach child & family needs, multiple activities completed in one visit, improved staff & family dynamics, improved communication with</p> <p>HCP, better connection with local resources</p> <p>CC Process: Assessment of family's housing, transportation, social & financial needs</p> <p>Referral for community services</p> <p>Follow ups completed timely CC effectiveness: No formal measure of CC impact; only pt./family</p>	<p>Limitations: Sm sample 7 of 121 US clinic participated</p> <p>Focus group underrepresentation of CG with strong opposing sentiments</p> <p>No outcome measurement of effective CC</p> <p>Notes: CC SB clinic is complex, time and labor intensive</p> <p>CC reduces challenges/issues for families</p> <p>ACA advocates for CC and Case Management to enhance HC and improve health outcomes</p>

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
Evaluate the ability of nurse CC to improve medical home utilization by pediatric patients post Katrina (Berry et al., 2011)	Prospective study	92 families participated 8 clinic staff completed QI survey	Surveys Medical home index QI tool The HOMES Complexity Index to determine the complexity of each child's case for CC Level of CC activity each child required MHFI measured the services each family received	Satisfaction formally measured Pre-Katrina HOMES Complexity Index-score 7.2 with 71-10 = high complexity Post-Katrina 61% CC contacts and 39% Md contacts MHFI: Pre Katrina-Md were family centered and available, Post Katrina increase in families obtaining CC	Limitations: Loss data d/t Katrina disaster, unable to measure if CC decreased ER visits or hospital stays post Katrina because less hospitals were available Conclusion: CC can be challenging, beneficial to have a CC Coordinator on staff, important to classify each child's acuity level for team effort in providing CC
Examine the relationship b/t CC, children with unmet health care needs, and family medical clinic (Litt & McCormick, 2015)	Quantitative study	34,249 children with special needs screened Participants 60% Boys 76% Caucasian	National random survey Successful CC received Received care from medical clinic Child's current health condition Existence of unmet service need	42% parents received CC at medical clinic, 37% children had min. of one functional disability, 20% of children with at least 1 unmet need CC decreased disability OR 0.71 (0.66, 0.76) Unmet needs increases odds of experiencing disability OR 1.93 95% CI (0.96, 0.98)	Limitations: Trend relationship CC & disability can't be determined from survey data Child disability was self-reported by parents not by medical documentation Conclusion: Intervention programs & CC can decrease

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
<p>Examine doctor's view on barriers/attitude regarding CC in primary care</p> <p>(Tschudy et al., 2016)</p>	<p>Quantitative study</p> <p>IV: views on obstacles to CC</p>	<p>Snow ball sampling Pediatricians (N = 572)</p> <p>Setting-ambulatory offices & clinics</p> <p>CC coordinators (N = 25)</p> <p>Primacy care medical clinics</p>	<p>Cross sectional survey (N = 874 surveys)</p> <p>Measured: barriers to CC & attitudes regarding CC activities</p> <p>On line focus group discussion</p> <p>Coordinator description of their role in CC</p> <p>Coordinator views on barriers & enablers to CC</p>	<p>Lack of staff to complete CC activities (OR 0.53), complete treatment records (OR, 0.51), referrals (OR 0.42)</p> <p>Lack communication abilities (OR, 0.56)</p> <p>Lack of time (OR, 0.53)</p> <p>Coordinators-task include recognizing those who need CC, pt. follow up, giving social care, sharing pt. information, assisting physicians</p>	<p>effect of chronic conditions</p> <p>CC services increase access & care utilization for CSHCN</p> <p>Limitations: No clinical data collected, unable to reveal what clinical outcomes can come from CC</p> <p>Conclusion: Positive views could not get pass the perceived obstacles of CC</p>
<p>Explain the views of staff on their profession & what enables or prevents CC in primary care</p> <p>(Friedman et al., 2016)</p>	<p>Qualitative study</p>	<p>Purposive sampling (N = 53)</p> <p>Patients (N = 20) Staff (N = 4) HCP (N = 29)</p> <p>Teaching hospital in Sydney</p>	<p>Semi structured interviews and focus groups</p> <p>Patients/families experience in cancer CC, view of CC, management of their care by CC activities and challenges</p>	<p>Barriers-mal unction IT systems, lack of community resources, increase workloads, having to complete other staff roles, no time for data entry, bad family interactions, hard to measure successful outcomes</p>	<p>Limitations: On line data was dependent on user's IT abilities</p> <p>Limited ability to follow themes</p> <p>Conclusion: working IT systems, available resources, relationships with HCP and family,</p>

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
Examine the views and lived experiences in CC for cancer care (Walsh et al., 2010)	Qualitative study	Asthmatic children from CC programs (N = 805) Los Angeles, Chicago, Philadelphia, San Juan	HCP view on what are CC activities, identify their role in doing CC, CC needs in urban & rural areas Patient interviews & structured comparison group Measured asthma signs & medical care used	Facilitators- Good staff relationships, establish team goals, good family interactions, self-care practices in place Confusion of various team member's jobs & responsibilities Team discussions to share pertinent information was beneficial Disparities in health service access noted	self-care practices all contribute to effective CC activity Note: Education should focus on the identified areas Limitations: Response rate among care coordinators was low (33%) Conclusion: Obstacles to CC were ineffective team work & lack of referral resources Communication is poor among HCP
To determine the impact of CC on asthma (Janevic et al., 2016)	Quasi experimental study IV: EB asthma CC activities, education, referrals, home visits	HCP (Physician, Pas & APNs)	Each patient contact/activity	Limited community resources Decrease in day & night symptoms a month (2.1, 1.2 symptoms a month) (p = <0.001) Decrease ED visits (3.2 times/past year) Decrease in hospitalizations (2.0 times/past year)	Limitations: Lack of data on the Latino control group on ED/hospitalizations was excluded Control grp data was from seven years ago; they did not represent cities from the study Conclusion: Asthma CC improved pediatric

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
<p>Explained CC measurement tool & activities</p> <p>(Connor et al., 2018)</p>	<p>Quantitative study</p> <p>IV: CC measurement tool</p>	<p>Pediatric cardiology ambulatory clinic</p>	<p>Cost savings</p>	<p>Time for each patient contact was average 15 minutes</p> <p>Complexities of contacts were 43% mild, 44.2% moderate, 9.3% severe</p> <p>Adverse outcomes prevented by CC- 267/567, 98 urgent care & 49 ER visits avoided,</p> <p>Savings due to prevented adverse outcome was \$550458, prevented care utilization \$158564 for UC & \$153566 ER</p>	<p>outcomes for children with asthma</p> <p>Increase amount of external validity</p> <p>Limitations: Lacks generalizability, staff reporting may be over/under, cost savings is based on est. of normal cost</p> <p>Conclusion: CCMT allowed CC to be quantified, there is no current literature to compare</p> <p>CC in pediatric neurology, gastroenterology and perioperative setting implemented the same tool</p> <p>There is a need to measure nursing activities to clarify and highlight the value of nursing care</p>

Notes: C.C. = care coordination, CG = caregiver, CSHCN = children with special healthcare needs, CWS = child welfare system, FC = foster care, FP = foster parent, HC = healthcare, IT = information technology, LACDCFS = Los Angeles county, department of children and family services Md = medical doctors, PHN = public health nurse SW = social worker.

Evidence Table 3

Collaboration

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
Examine the expertise students & professionals develop & gain when collaborating for child protection (Hood et al., 2017)	Qualitative study	<p>Purposive sampling Equal number of representations (N = 18)</p> <p>Student group (n = 3 nurses, n = 3 SWs, n = 3 teachers)</p> <p>Professional group (n = 3 nurses, n = 3 SWs, n = 3 teachers)</p> <p>All interviews were completed at the University</p>	<p>Semi-structured interviews Student & professional nurses, SWs, & teacher's perception and experiences of interprofessional collaboration</p> <p>Clinical scenarios and critical incident illustrations were used to lead the interviews</p>	<p>2 categories and 7 themes emerged Conception of their practice: Lack knowledge other professional roles comfortable in decisions, SWs concerned with child protection, nurses & teachers lack confidence in risk assessment</p> <p>Managing & communication in relationships influenced differently by parents & child -Professional grp was child-centered</p>	<p>Limitations: Not generalizable, sm. sample size of each group</p> <p>Conclusion: All groups gained knowledge & skills from interprofessional collaboration</p> <p>Sm difference between students & professionals in handling relationships</p> <p>Note: Ethnographic data would have helped put the findings in better context</p>
Explain & evaluate nurse-led IPC model & viewpoint and knowledge gained from inter-professional staff/clinicians (Selleck et al., 2017)	Qualitative study	Professional staff (nurses, SW, optometrist, dietitian, physicians, mental health providers, informatics specialist, pharmaceutical pt. assistance program coordinator)	<p>3 structured timed interval interviews using case study method</p> <p>Obtain clinicians baseline view understanding of IPCP guidelines & previous</p>	<p>Clinicians improved their knowledge on IPEC from clinic experiences</p> <p>Increased clinic teamwork</p>	<p>Limitations: Sm sample size from one IPCP model-based clinic</p> <p>Participant bias toward IPC care</p> <p>Variability d/t attrition and staff replacement,</p>

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
Identify IPE as a student translates theory into professional practice (Ketcherside, Rhodes, Powelson, Cox, & Parker, 2017)	10-year retrospective study DV: IPE home health visiting education IV: Attitudes and perception on collaborative abilities	Clinic staff: -16 Caucasians, 6 A.A., 2 Asians, 1 Biracial -4 males, 21 females Providing Access to Healthcare (PATH) Clinic 148 participants Group 1, (N = 34) community/PH professionals Group 2, (N =114) registered nurses Midwestern University	employment with other HC professional types from the clinic Evaluate clinician's current knowledge of IPCP guidelines from education & experience Document & evaluate Inter-professional relationship development & progress Surveys 24- item Inter-professional socialization & valuing scale 24- item Inter-professional socialization & valuing scale 5-point Likert scale "Ability to work with others," 5-point Likert scale Value & comfort in working with others at work	Patient's medical, social, & financial needs addressed More respect & learned for each other's profession Repeating errors minimized Pt.'s perceived more time with HCP & thorough services PH professional higher mean score in value & comfort working with others (49.5, SD = 4.3) Both groups positive attitudes belief in their capabilities to IPC (p = .01)	limited staff who completed all 3 interviews Conclusions: IPCP model effective in comprehensive team-based care Inter-professional relationships improved pt. outcomes Limitations: Sm sample size, not generalizable, limits accuracy of statistical data Lacks validity, self-reported data Increased IP skills may be from work experience, not student IPE Conclusion: IPE should extend into the professional level

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
				Both groups perceive IPP is challenging in the workplace	
Explore the values of two facility managers one a nurse, one a SW (Dunworth & Kirwan, 2012)	Qualitative study	Direct care staff/assistants (N = 65) participants Setting both care facilities	Structured questionnaire survey Moral conflict situational vignettes	Staff at both homes SW/Nurse managed home want best outcomes for facility residents SW-managed home staff more engaged in moral conflict resolution	Limitations: Sm study, not generalizable Conclusion: No difference in value base b/t Nurse & SW Note: Health/social training helpful
Examine IPE of medical and social worker students (Gould, Lee, Berkowitz, & Bronstein, 2015)	Mixed method triangulation design	Medical students, residents, social worker students Binghamton University, NY	Pre/Post test administered for the IPC adapted for HC 3 Focus groups 1 interview	IPE caused changed views on IPC ($p = .02$), increased IPC after the IPE & consideration to teamwork ($p = .02$), more appreciation for other's professional role Effective communication among all the students contributed to better patient healthcare Barrier to IPC is frequent scheduling of pt.	Limitation: Time & communication are barriers to effective IPC Conclusion: IPE made student more aware of IPC process Notes: IPE provided better health care to pts., a more thorough view on pt. needs

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
Examine views of inter-professional teams on collaboration in CWS in terms of dilemmas (Rose, 2011)	Qualitative study	8 inter-professional teams from different areas of children services -54 interviews -1 focus grp	Semi-structured interviews Focus groups Solutions to challenges in role, identity & control	Role-assign universal roles to team members irrespective of knowledge Identity-combining expertise gives a holistic approach to meeting HC goals Control-team decisions brings authority and cohesiveness	Limitations: Difference b/t description and practice is hard to assess Conclusion: Collaboration is not easily practice specialist may have to listen to non-specialist Notes: Having joint goals leads to greater resolution to dilemmas,
Explore CPS staff's (SW) perceptions of collaborative practices (Lalayants, 2013)	Qualitative study	Purposive sampling CPS staff (N = 90) New York City, NY	Interviews Domains examined: Collaborative construct procedures, factors, & situations that support & impede collaborations Collaborative improvement requests	CPS SW lacked knowledge on role of other CPS professionals CPS SW lacked time to consult Lack of CPS mandate & motivation of SW was a barrier to consults Communication is important component of collaboration Strong & committed leaders is vital to staff & consultant collaboration	Limitations: Small sample, lacks generalizability Perception not actual practice of collaboration was analyzed Conclusion: Commitment, leadership, communication, mutual goals, & resources is needed for successful collaboration Notes: Building trusting relationships &

Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Limitations, Conclusion & Notes
<p>Explore the collaboration issues b/t PHNs, doctors, midwives, CPW in varying county sizes</p> <p>(Clancy et al., 2013)</p>	Qualitative study	<p>PHNs, doctors, midwives, & CPW (n = 1596)</p> <p>Norwegian</p>	<p>Questionnaires</p> <p>6-point Likert scale to assess collaborative activity</p> <p>Factors important to collaboration</p>	<p>Location-physical proximity, trust, respect, open communication & collaborative</p> <p>Skills are important in collaborative practice</p> <p>MH professional were missing in collaborative practice</p> <p>The smaller the county, the easier to manage collaboration activities</p> <p>4 themes, professional responsibilities follow up responses, collaboration, staff requirements, & education</p>	<p>interest in having successful outcomes enhances collaboration</p> <p>Limitations: The larger counties were under represented</p> <p>Conclusion: Not all counties organize services in a way that is favorable to collaboration & counties do not f/u on problems</p> <p>Notes: Coordination is activities that organize services</p> <p>Collaboration is working together</p>
<p>Examine enabling factors & obstacles to communication & collaboration to CC</p> <p>(Dudley, Wallhagen, Ritchie, & Rehm, 2016)</p>	Qualitative study	<p>Snowball sampling</p> <p>Primary care & palliative providers (n = 10)</p>	Semi-structured interviews		<p>Conclusion: Delineated roles, continuous face to face interactions, staff education on health topic & care</p>

Notes: A.A. = African American, CPS = child protective services, CWS = child welfare system, HC = healthcare, HCP = healthcare provider, IPC = Interprofessional collaboration, IPCP = interprofessional collaboration practice, MH = mental health, PH = public health, PHN = public health nurse, SW = social work.

APPENDIX B
PROJECT TIMELINE

APPENDIX C

LOS ANGELES COUNTY DPH IRB APPROVAL LETTER

COUNTY OF LOS ANGELES

Public Health

BOARD OF SUPERVISORS

Hilda L. Solis
First DistrictMark Ridley-Thomas
Second DistrictSheila Kushi
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Chief Science Officer**J. Walton Senterfitt, Ph.D., R.N., M.P.H.**
Institutional Review Board
Chair and Administrator
313 North Figueroa Street, Room 127
Los Angeles, California 90012
TEL (213) 288-7785

Public Health & Health Services Institutional Review Board

TO: Lisa Jenkins Baughman, RN, PHN, BSN
Principal Investigator

FROM: J. Walton Senterfitt, PhD, MPH
Chairman, LAC Public Health & Health Services Institutional Review Board (IRB)

Project title: Public Health Nurses Enhancing Outcomes among Foster Care Children

Action taken: Approval and Classification as Exempt as Research of an Exempt Type
Action taken by: Chairman, LAC Public Health & Health Services Institutional Review Board
Action date: September 5, 2018

Annual report due: September 4, 2019

As Chairman of the Los Angeles County Public Health and Health Services Administration IRB, I have reviewed your above-referenced application comprising the use of focus groups and subject matter experts to develop a nursing practice guideline aimed at enhancing care coordination activity of Public Health Nurses (PHNs) among children and youth in foster care, and then subsequently to implement and evaluate the guidelines among a select group of PHNs. I have determined that the project meets the minimum criteria for approval in that it addresses an important public health and health services issue, with appropriate methodology and adequate protection for the rights and welfare of participants. I have also determined that the study poses no more than minimal risk to individuals, and is eligible for classification as exempt, in the "research of an exempt type" category, per IRB policies and federal regulations 45 CFR 46.101 (b) (1) (categories 2 and 4).

Therefore, the project is approved and classified as research of an exempt type. Your project is exempt from detailed compliance with federal Common Rule regulations, including obtaining written informed consent or applying for a waiver. However, the project must comply with all principles of the ethical conduct of research and research-related activities, including obtaining effective informed consent in an appropriate form and the careful protection of the data obtained and used. The verbal consent script meets the requirements for effective consent.

September 5, 2018
Lisa Jenkins Baughman, RN, PHN, BSN
IRB Project No. 2018-08-760
Page 2 of 2

I concur with your assertion that no PHI will be collected or transmitted and therefore no HIPAA individual authorization or waiver application is necessary.

In the event you make changes to this approved protocol, you must submit such changes to the IRB for approval and confirmation of the continuing exemption criteria before the changes may be implemented.

You must also submit to the IRB a brief summary final report when the project is completed, including copies of any submitted manuscripts or formal presentations. If the project is not yet complete at the end of one year, then please submit an interim status progress report each year until the project is completed.

APPENDIX D

LOS ANGELES COUNTY DCFS APPROVAL LETTER

BOBBY D. CAGLE
Director

BRANDON T. NICHOLS
Chief Deputy Director

County of Los Angeles
DEPARTMENT OF CHILDREN AND FAMILY SERVICES

425 Shatto Place, Los Angeles, California 90020
(213) 351-5602

Board of Supervisors
HILDA L. SOLIS
First District
MARK RIDLEY-THOMAS
Second District
SHEILA KUEHL
Third District
JANICE HAHN
Fourth District
KATHRYN BARGER
Fifth District

September 21, 2018

Ms. Lisa Jenkins Baughman
921 E. Compton Blvd.
Compton, CA 90221

RE: Research Approval

Dear Ms. Baughman,

On behalf of Department of Children and Family Services, the System Improvement and Research Section, I am pleased to notify our approval of your research study entitled, "Public Health Nurses Enhancing Outcomes among Foster Care Children."

The purpose of this research is to develop, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based nursing practice guideline at DCFS Compton and Torrance offices to enhance the care coordination activity of public health nurses (PHNs) and medical and dental compliance rates among children and youth in foster care.

The research will employ qualitative and quantitative methods. It includes interviews with the focus group of PHNs and CSWs from Torrance and Compton offices as well as quantitative data analysis.

Please update us if there are any changes to the research plan. If you have any questions about the approval, please contact Sophia Lee at (562) 345-6680 or lees@dcfs.lacounty.gov.

Sincerely,

Amy Kim
Children Services Administrator III
System Improvement and Research Section

APPENDIX E

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY FULLERTON IRB PPROVAL

IRB #: HSR-18-19-136

Title: Public Health Nurses Enhancing Outcomes of Care Coordination Among Children in Foster Care

Creation Date: 9-6-2018

End Date: 10-5-2019

Status: **Approved**

Principal Investigator: Lisa Baughman

Review Board: Expedited Board

Sponsor:

Study History

Submission Type	Initial	Review Type	Expedited	Decision	Approved
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Key Study Contacts

Member	Lisa Baughman	Role	Principal Investigator	Contact	baughman@csu.fullerton.edu
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Member	Lisa Baughman	Role	Primary Contact	Contact	baughman@csu.fullerton.edu
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Member	Penny Weismuller	Role	Co-Principal Investigator	Contact	pweismuller@fullerton.edu
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APPENDIX F

DNP PROJECT FOCUS GROUP FLYER

CSW Focus Group

October 25th, 2018, 12pm-1pm

*** LUNCH PROVIDED**

DCFS Torrance Office
2325 Crenshaw Blvd
Torrance, Ca 90501
Location: Conference Room A/B

Please confirm your attendance via email
[Lisa Baughman 562/477-0994 or 310/668-6596]

Topic: PHNs and CSWs collaborating to improve health outcomes of children and youth in foster care

APPENDIX G

DNP PROJECT FOCUS GROUP CONSENT

California State University Fullerton

Research Study Consent Form

Study Title: Public Health Nurses Enhancing Outcomes of Care Coordination among Children in Foster Care

Protocol Number: HSR-18-19-136

Researchers: Lisa Baughman, MSN, RN, PHN, Doctoral student, School of Nursing
Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN, PHN, Faculty, School of Nursing

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Lisa Baughman, a Doctor of Nursing Practice student and Penny Weismuller, a Professor in the School of Nursing at California State University, Fullerton. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

This research study is being conducted to enhance health outcomes of care coordination among children in foster care by understanding how Social Workers and Public Health Nurses see care coordination. You are being asked to take part because you are a Social Worker or a Public Health Nurse working with children in foster care. Taking part in the study will take about 45-60 minutes. You cannot take part in this study if you are under 18 years of age.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the study, you will be asked to participate in a focus group discussing care coordination for children in foster care. You will be asked about current care coordination and if you see ways care coordination could be improved. You will be asked to keep focus group discussions confidential.

This project will be using voice recordings of the focus group discussion. If you wish a summary of focus group discussion, the researchers will provide one to you at the conclusion of the study.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

There is no direct benefit to you from being in this study. If you take part in the study, you may help improve care coordination for children in foster care.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

There are no identifiable risks in this study.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study are being collected confidentially. **Confidentiality will be provided to the extent allowed by the law.**

A voice recording will be made of the focus group discussion. This is required for you to be in the study.

The results of this study may be published or presented at professional meetings, but the identities of all research participants will remain anonymous

The data for this study will be kept for 3 years after completion of the study. Data will be used for professional presentations or publications.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study.

You will receive a \$10 gift card for taking part in this study. If you decide to quit the study, you will receive \$10 gift card.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Lisa Baughman at (562) 477-0994 or baughman@csu.fullerton.edu or Penny Weismuller at 657-278-5740 or pweismuller@fullerton.edu. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or questions that make you uncomfortable or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or I have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form to keep.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

Your signature below indicates that you are giving permission to audio/video tape your responses.

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

APPENDIX H
DNP PROJECT FOCUS GROUP QUESTIONNAIRE

DNP Project
Focus Group Questionnaire

Moderator (Lisa Baughman)

Assistant (Dr. Penny Weismuller)

Public Health Nurses (PHN)/Social Workers (SW) : Topics will examine PHN's or SW's perceptions, thoughts, and understanding of care coordination and their role in care coordination

Topic Area #1 Perception of care coordination

- What does care coordination mean to you and how would you define it?
- What role does the PHN and CSW have in care coordination?
- Should Social Workers (SW) be a part of the care coordination process? if so, what does, or should that look like; if not, why not?
- How do PHNs and SWs collaborate in the care coordination process?

Topic Area #2 Challenges and barriers

- What do you see as challenges and barriers to care coordination?
- What do you need to overcome challenges and barrier to care coordination?
- Do you think the will/motivation exist within the system to address and change the challenges and barriers?

Topic Area #3 Quality improvement

- What would make care coordination better for you?

- What part should the caregiver play, if any at all, when addressing quality improvement needs in care coordination?

Social Workers (SW): Topics to understand the SWs perceptions and thoughts of care coordination and their role in care coordination

Topic Area #1 Perceptions of care coordination

- What does care coordination mean to you and how would you define it?
- What role does the CSW and PHN have in care coordination?
- Should Social Workers (SW) be a part of the care coordination process? if so, what does, or should that look like; if not, why not?
- How do PHNs and SWs collaborate in the care coordination process?

Topic Area #2 Challenges and barriers

- What do you see as challenges and barriers to care coordination?
- What do you need to overcome challenges and barrier to care coordination?
- Do you think the will/motivation exist within the system to address and change the challenges and barriers?

Topic Area #3 Quality improvement

- What would make care coordination better for you?
- What part should the caregiver play, if any at all, when addressing quality improvement needs in care coordination?

APPENDIX I

REVISED CWPHNP PRACTICE GUIDELINE

COUNTY OF LOS ANGELES
DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH SERVICES • CHILDREN’S MEDICAL
SERVICES (CMS)
CHILD WELFARE PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING PROGRAM (CWPHNP)
POLICY AND PROCEDURE
NURSING

CWPHNP

EFFECTIVE DATE	REVISED
December 1, 2018 to February 28, 2019	11/26/2

SUBJECT: PUBLIC HEALTH NURSE (PHN): ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

PURPOSE: The Department of Children and Family Services (DCFS) consults with Child Welfare PHNs from the Department of Public Health (DPH). PHNs work in collaboration with Children’s Social Workers (CSWs) to facilitate appropriate health care services for children in the child welfare system.

ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE CHILD WELFARE PHN:

Children in Home-of-Parent Placement

1. PHNs are responsible for responding to requests for PHN consultations from CSWs regarding children living in any of the following settings:
 - a. Kin-Gap
 - b. Non-Court Probate Case
 - c. Legal Guardian, Non-Court
 - d. Post-Adoption Services (PAS) Case
 - e. Voluntary Family Reunification (VFR)
 - f. Non-Court Family Reunification
 - g. Voluntary Permanent Placement (PP)

- h. With a biological parent, including through Emergency Response (ER) referrals, Voluntary Family Maintenance (VFM), or Family Maintenance (FM)
2. PHNs are responsible for tasks that include, but are not limited to, the following:
 - a. ER Referrals**
 - 1) Consult with the ER CSW about the child's medical and developmental problems as part of the Joint Response Referral (JRR) process during the investigative phase for children with known or suspected problems.
 - 2) Participate in joint face-to-face visits with the CSW in the home, office, school, or hospital and obtain and review the child's medical condition with the CSW, including reviewing medical records. Consult with the medical provider, as needed.
 - 3) Provide recommendations about the child's medical, developmental, and mental health needs, as needed and requested.
 - 4) Document medical information and, if applicable, mental health information related to prescribed and administered psychotropic medication(s), in the Health Notebook/HEP in the CWS/CMS.
 - 5) Assist in the coordination of necessary medical follow-up.
 - b. HUB (The Out-stationed Medical Hub PHN reports to a Public Health Nursing Supervisor and/or Nurse Manager)**
 - 1) Identify and prioritize health care follow up and care coordination needs for children served by the Medical Hub through regular communication with Medical Hub staff and use of professional expertise in review of Hub medical examination results.
 - 2) For Cases with an immediate or high priority need and as capacity allows, provide care coordination services for conditions found during Medical Hub assessments, to include medical, dental, nutritional, developmental and mental health needs. The PHN will consult with the Medical Hub providers on prioritizing and will use their collective judgment to determine which needs are immediate and highest priority and could be best accomplished by the on-site PHN rather than sending to the regional PHN.

- 3) Care coordination activities may include but are not limited to facilitating and assisting in:
 - a. Maintaining compliance with Hub medical provider medical plans/recommendations and specialty referral follow ups;
 - b. Addressing barriers that impact continuity of health care services;
 - c. Communicating as needed with Regional Center, California Children Services (CCS), Fetal Alcohol Syndrome clinic services, and other agencies;
 - d. Obtaining copies of health care and immunization records, as needed;
 - e. Coordinating with the regional CSW on HIV consent process;
 - f. Following up with recommended tests and referrals;
 - g. Verifying support services from medically fragile children;
 - h. Providing health education resources and anticipatory guidance;
- 4) Assist in ongoing care coordination activities for DCFS-involved children for whom the Hub serves as the Medical Home.
- 5) Document care coordination activities and information in E-mHub and CWS/CMS computerized systems, as appropriate.
- 6) Communicate with the assigned Regional Office PHN via a Hub-DCFS Nurse-to Nurse report form.
- 7) Other duties as mutually agreed upon by DCFS, DHS and the PHN Supervisor.

c. Open VFM, FM, VFR, and Non-Court Probate Cases

- 1) Consult with the CSW for a child with known or suspected medical or developmental conditions as part of the JRR process.

d. Post-Adoption Services Cases and Kin-Gap Cases

- 1) Review medical information to determine eligibility for Specialized Care Increment (SCI) F-Rate criteria.

e. Children with Special Health Care Needs

- 1) Review the medical records for children with serious and/or chronic medical and developmental conditions, in order to assist CSWs in making informed decisions and arranging and planning services with regard to screening, assessment, and treatment of the child's condition.
- 2) Assess the child's medical condition for Medical Case Management Services (MCMS) Unit transfer criteria and for Specialized Care Increment (SCI) F-Rate criteria.

- 3) Participate in Multi-Disciplinary Team meetings [i.e., Child and Family Team (CFT)], as needed to develop a plan of care for children.

f. Hospitalized Children

- 1) Provide weekly written updates to Public Health Nurse Supervisor (PHNS), Nurse Manager, and CSWs to:
 - a) Assess current health status of child.
 - b) Monitor and track the child's readiness for hospital discharge.
- 2) Assess the caregiver's capacity to meet the child's ongoing medical needs and continuity of care during in-person CSW joint visit.

g. Critical Incidents and Child Fatalities

- 1) Complete a joint CSW visit to assess the medical, developmental, and mental health needs of all children residing in the home, as needed.
- 2) Assist in obtaining current and past medical information on the child and his/her siblings.
- 3) Consult with medical providers regarding the child's medical condition and recommend necessary medical services for the child, as needed.
- 4) Provide a written summary medical report to the PHNS and Nurse Manager as per the Public Health Nurse Documentation Standards for Critical Incident policy.

h. Additional Responsibilities

- 1) Review E-m Hub exam results and document the results in the CWS/CMS Health Notebook/HEP as per the PHN Documentation Policy, and WCPHN Instructional Manual.
 - a) Review and document forensic exam findings in the CWS/CMS Contact Notebook.
 - b) Clarify and explain findings and results to the CSW, as needed.
- 2) Provide trainings on the role of the PHN.
- 3) Provide F-Rate training to foster parents, relatives, and caregivers.

Children in Out-of-Home Placement

1. PHNs are responsible for responding to requests for PHN consultations from CSWs regarding children living in any of the following settings:

2. PHNs serve as consultants to CSWs and health advocates for children placed in any of the following:
 - a. Permanent Placement, Court-involved
 - b. Emergency Response (ER) Referrals, Court-detained
 - c. Foster Family Agency (FFA) Certified Home-Family Reunifications, Permanent Placement
 - d. Foster Family Home (FFH)-Family Reunification, Permanent Placement
 - e. Short-Term Residential Therapeutic Program (STRTP), Reunification, Court-detained
 - f. Legal Guardian Home, Court-involved
 - g. Small Family Home-Family Reunification
 - h. Tribal Court-Specified Homes-Family Reunification, Permanent Placement
 - i. Kin-Gap-Family Reunification, Permanent Placement
3. PHNs are responsible for tasks that include, but are not limited to, the following:
 - a. **Consultation and Assessment**
 - 1) Respond to consultation request within three to five working days as per PHN Consultation Procedure/Policy
 - 2) Identify chronic physical, developmental, dental, and mental health conditions in a child.
 - 3) Review and assess medical, dental, developmental, and mental health care documents, including the Child Welfare Services/Case Management System (CWS/CMS) Health Notebook/Health and Education Passport (HEP), to:
 - a) Identify a child's appropriate health care needs.
 - b) Determine appropriate referrals and services needed for the child.
 - c) Evaluate the health status of a child in out-of-home care.
 - d) Assist in making Specialized Care Increment (SCI) F-Rate eligibility recommendations.
 - e) Evaluate and prioritize his/her caseload according to the PHN Practice Manual Guidelines.
 - 4) Review the DCFS Statistics & Information Transmitted Everyday (SITE) monthly for your assigned FC children and youth who are out of DCFS medical and dental compliance according to Bright Futures and American Academy of Pediatrics Recommendations for Preventive Pediatric Health Care.

- a) Identify children who require current medical or dental examination.
- b) Provide the report to the assigned CSW/SCSW.
- c) Review child's medical file for completed medical/dental exam reports/records.

b. Collaboration and Evaluation

- 1) Collaborate with assigned CSW to determine and discuss appropriate plan required to bring child's health exams into compliance.
- 2) Collaborate with foster families, CSWs, POs, and health care providers to facilitate referrals to health and mental health care providers.
- 3) Identify appropriate health care services and community resources for a child.
- 4) Collaborate with community agencies, health and mental health care programs, and caregivers to maintain a child's continuity of care.
 - a) Assist CSWs and POs in obtaining additional resources to provide services to a child/children and youth.
- 5) Provide education about the role of the PHNs and medical topics, upon request, to caregivers, community providers, POs, and CSWs.
- 6) Provide all follow-up reports and relevant documentation for Critical Incident (CI) and Child Fatality (CF) meetings.

c. Coordination of Services

- 1) Primary and specialty health care needs.
- 2) Medical services for a medically fragile child.
- 3) Contact and coordinate with caregiver/resource family to schedule required medical and dental exams and document appointment in CWS/CMS Contacts as per PHN Documentation Policy.
- 4) Coordinate necessary medical follow-up by reviewing Enterprise-medical Hub (Em Hub) exam results.
- 5) Assist in providing monitoring and oversight of psychotropic medication in order to aid in the planning and coordination of health care services as per policy.

d. Documentation

- 1) Document all health information in the CWS/CMS per PHN Documentation Policy.
- 2) Document any prescribed and administered psychotropic medication(s).
- 3) Provide weekly written updates to the Children's Hospital Log regarding the status of a hospitalized child placed in out-of-home care.
- 4) Actively review and update the Health Notebook/HEP based on medical information obtained from providers in the CWS/CMS.
 - a) Document Em Hub exam results in the Health Notebook/HEP.
- 5) Complete a Nurse-to-Nurse (N2N) Report of the child's health care coordination status when transferring a case to another PHN.

e. Participation

- 1) Participate in SCSW unit and/or ARA section meetings to educate DCFS on the role of PHNs, various health topics, current pertinent nursing policies/procedures.
- 2) Attend joint home, office, school, and hospital visits, with CSW as needed.
- 3) Attend Multi-Disciplinary Team meetings [i.e., Child and Family Team (CFT)], as needed, to establish a plan of care.
- 4) Assist as needed, NMDs in making informed decisions regarding his/her health care by, at a minimum, providing educational resources and materials.

REFERENCE(S):

1. Children's Hospital Log Policy
2. Joint Response Referral Consulting with PHN (DCFS Policy 0070-560.05; revision date: 7/1/14)
3. Nurse-to-Nurse (N2N) Policy
4. PHN Documentation Standards for Critical Incident (CI), Child Fatality (CF), Near Fatality (NF), and Media Alert Referrals
5. PHN Practice Manual Guidelines Specialized Care Increment (SCI) F-Rate Policy

**APPROVED FOR THE TERM OF DECEMBER 1ST, 2018 THROUGH
FEBRUARY 28TH, 2019 ONLY
DCFS COMPTON AND TORRANCE OFFICE**

APPROVED: *Monette Antonio-McCullough*
11/262018

DATE:

NURSE MANAGER

APPROVED: _____
CMS NURSING DIRECTOR

DATE:

APPENDIX J

PHN EDUCATION (POWER POINT SLIDES)

**Public Health Nurses
Enhancing Outcomes of
Care Coordination among
Foster Care Children**

Lisa Jenkins Baughman, MSN, MSHCM, RN, FNP-BC, PHN,
Southern California DNP Consortium, California State University, Fullerton
DNP Project

1

Objectives

- ▶ Define and discuss the benefits of a health advocate related to the PHN role
- ▶ Understand the importance of children receiving timely medical/dental care
- ▶ Discuss the focus group results
- ▶ Review revised CWPHN PHN Roles and Responsibilities Policy
- ▶ Discuss the process in receiving access to DCFS SITE application and review the steps to assess assign unit statistical data
- ▶ Identify and discuss additional strategies to improve consultations, collaboration and coordination related to the PHN role

2

Background

- ▶ LACDCFS policy requires that all children entering FC have an initial medical assessment within 24 hours of placement
- ▶ Comprehensive physical exam within 30 days and every year thereafter unless the child is younger than 24 months of age or their medical condition requires more frequent monitoring and care.
- ▶ A dental exam completed beginning at one-year of age and every year after
- ▶ Literature shows that children in the foster care do not receive suitable and timely health care. (Child Welfare Information Gateway, 2017)

3

**Significance
(Medical)**

- ▶ Up to 80% of children entering FC have unmet needs for medical conditions, with asthma and diabetes mellitus being the most neglected. (Schneidman, Smith, & Patrasca, 2012; Szilagyi et al., 2015)
- ▶ Children in FC are more likely to have the following:
 - ▶ Obesity (18%)
 - ▶ Asthma (24%)
 - ▶ Visual and hearing deficits (7.3%) (Turney & Wildeman, 2016)
- ▶ 88% of children in FC require a referral to a healthcare specialist for more detailed assessment, monitoring, and/or treatment of medical conditions. (Deutsch & Fortin, 2015)

4

**Significance
(Dental)**

- ▶ Children in FC receive irregular dental care and tend to have more dental caries and poorer oral health than children residing at home with biological parent. (Gibbs, Hooton, Chi, Hinderberger, & Miguez, 2013)
- ▶ 40% of children in FC also have significant dental problems. (Szilagyi et al., 2015)
- ▶ Unmet dental needs can cause tooth decay which can lead to medical conditions such as sinus and ear infection.
- ▶ Poor dental health can impair a child's ability to focus, thus leading to poor school performance.

5

Compliance

LACDCFS goal for both medical and dental examination compliance is 90%.

LACDCFS Medical and Dental Compliance Rates Updated 11/26/18

LACDCFS Office	Medical Compliance	Dental Compliance
American Indian Unit	90%	86%
Santa Fe Springs	77%	59%
Glendora	75%	52%
Pomona	72%	49%
Compton	52%	28%
Torrance	48%	27%

6

**Focus Groups
(Results)**

- ▶ Open communication among PHN, CSW, CG, HCP is key to appropriate and meaningful care coordination for children in FC
- ▶ Joint home visit promote an open relationship for PHNs with their CSW and the child's CG
- ▶ Need a more defined and clear PHN Roles & Responsibilities Policy
- ▶ Need additional education and training on the PHN Roles & Responsibilities Policy for more consistency among the PHNs
- ▶ Assure PHN access to DCFS the SITE and Orchid
- ▶ Establishing PHN unit ratios
- ▶ Update DCFS medical/dental examination forms

7

**PHN Role
(Consultant)**

Consultant

- ▶ Nursing consultation is defined as providing "advice, clarification, and guidance designed to facilitate the provision of routine well child care and treatment of medical concerns."
- ▶ In the CWPHN Program PHNs shall provide nursing consultation to the CSW and the child's primary CG and other multidisciplinary teams on the following nursing components:
 - ▶ Child's health care plan, health status, and treatment needs
 - ▶ Medical terminology and interpreting medical records
 - ▶ Accessing treatment services

(CWPHN Consultation Policy, 2017)

8

APPENDIX K
FUSION DATA COLLECTION

		HCPCFC - DATA								11/1/2017 to 1/31/2018
Item \ Month		PHN 1	PHN 2	PHN 3	PHN 4	PHN 5	PHN 6	PHN 7	PHN 8	TOTAL
Consultations	Consultation Total	100	64	119	139	175	173	171	240	1601
	Initial	19	16	8	23	9	35	22	17	189
	FollowUp	81	48	111	116	166	138	149	223	1412
Health Assessment /	Physical Exams	37	45	34	76	27	72	73	58	595
	Dental Exams	11	20	32	51	19	41	35	41	339
	Medical Home	36	70	93	136	27	145	98	110	954
	Medical Records	37	37	31	83	31	136	144	46	983
	JV-220/PMA	3	1	4	14	17	9	15	12	94
Communication	Communication	192	32	105	37	138	315	267	249	1801
	Email	129	10	6	9	58	120	103	4	589
	Phone	55	19	77	21	26	90	77	201	803
	Faxes	2	2	9	4	6	5	31	7	106
	In-person	6	1	13	3	48	100	56	37	303
Collaboration	Collaboration Total	3		4		2	15	5	12	46
	CFT	0		1		0	2	0	2	6
Acuity	Level 1	73	52	45	97	29	108	75	102	675
	Level 2	12	5	22	12	11	26	35	29	201
	Level 3	1	1	2	5	8	7	16	7	85
	Level 4	1	0	5	3	0	7	5	1	45

APPENDIX L**WESTERN INSTITUTE OF NURSING 2019 CONFERENCE**

win@confex.com

Mon, Dec 10, 2018, 1:53 PM

Dear Lisa Baughman,

Congratulations! Your abstract, "Public Health Nurses Enhance Outcomes of Care Coordination Among Foster Care Children," has been accepted for a poster presentation at the Western Institute of Nursing's 52nd Annual Communicating Nursing Research Conference to be held April 10-13, 2019 at the Town and Country Hotel and Convention Center in San Diego. Please notify any additional authors on your paper of this good news.

Your poster session is scheduled for Saturday, April 13, 2019 from 8:00 AM - 12:00 PM.

Conference registration is available [here](#) and a room at the Town and Country Hotel may be reserved [here](#). The conference program will be posted on the WIN website in the upcoming weeks.

Poster presentations are less formal, but not less rigorous or substantive, than podium presentations. Poster authors present their work interactively to groups of interested individuals with the aid of a visual display that summarizes research findings or project outcomes. Posters are displayed in a central location for four-hour blocks of time so attendees can peruse the visual displays and talk with the authors. The WIN Program Committee has set aside one hour of time during each poster session in which the only scheduled activity is poster viewing. We ask that presenters stand by their posters during this hour, which will be listed in the conference program. Poster boards are 4' x 8'. Please visit the Presenter's Corner on the WIN website for valuable tips on presenting your poster.

As the Presenting Author, we ask that you log into the Presenter Information Center ([link is below](#)) to give your consent to present (see the "Consent to Participate" module) by Friday, January 4. Poster presenters do not need to upload presentation files, so please disregard that module in the Presenter Information Center.

We look forward to an excellent conference and to your participation. If you have questions, please contact Bo Perry by email at perrybo@ohsu.edu.

Sincerely,

Katreena Collette Merrill, RN, PhD
Chair, WIN Program Committee

APPENDIX M

DPH 2019 PHN NURSING PRACTICE CONFERENCE

Barbara Ferrer, Ph.D., M.P.H., M.Ed.
Director

JEFFREY D. GUNZENHAUSER, M.D., M.P.H.
Interim Health Officer

CYNTHIA A. HARDING, M.P.H.
Chief Deputy Director

Wesley L. FORD, M.A., M.P.H.
Deputy Director, Health Promotion Bureau

ANNA LONG, Ph.D., M.P.H.
Director, Children's Medical Services
9320 Telstar Avenue, Suite 226, El Monte,
California 91731
TEL (626) 569-6001 • FAX (626) 569-1909

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Fifth District

Good Afternoon,

Congratulations! Lisa Jenkins Baughman your abstract (Public Health Nurses Enhancing Outcomes of Care Coordination Among Children and Youth in Foster Care) has been selected as a poster presentation for our 2019 PHN Nursing Practice Conference scheduled for Thursday May 9, 2019 at the Quiet Cannon in Montebello. Although we will not have judging or awards for this category this year, each participant will receive recognition for their participation.

I have attached some guidelines and pictures of sample posters from the past to assist you in putting your poster together. If you have any questions, please contact me via email and I will be happy to assist you.

Thanks,

Lisa

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